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Executive Summary

Persistent, mobile, and potentially toxic (PM(T)) substances in the soil-sediment-water system present a significant barrier to the reuse of natural resources and the realization of a safe circular economy in Europe. The scientific and technical solutions developed and optimized within PROMISCES are essential for dealing with PM(T) substances in the circular economy. However, the effective implementation of these solutions also depends on social and economic conditions, and the regulatory framework. Key conditions influencing implementation include having a clear regulatory target that needs to be satisfied by the solutions, clearly defined roles and responsibilities among authorities and stakeholders, and the availability of financial resources to support adoption.

Within the [PROMISCES project](#), a multidisciplinary approach was used to initiate the development of solution strategies that address these boundary conditions. Central to this effort are co-creation workshops designed to bring together diverse stakeholders to collaboratively identify challenges, evaluate solutions, and formulate strategies that have concrete actions. This deliverable provides guidance on how to co-create a solution strategy for dealing with PM(T)(s) in a circular economy. For this, we have used the experience and lessons learnt in the co-creation workshops organized within the PROMISCES project.

The PROMISCES workshops provided valuable lessons for co-creating solution strategies, with the main lessons being:

- A well-defined problem statement is important for organizing a successful co-creation process. For this, the role of local partners is essential in organizing successful workshops.
- Stakeholders from the entire circular economy (CE) route should be invited to participate in co-creation processes. This includes stakeholders who focus on more than just scientific and technical solutions for PM(T). Engaging a local partner is crucial for the identification of the relevant stakeholders.
- It is recommended that stakeholder interactions include or are followed up with political engagement, supporting the effective transition of suggested actions into a comprehensive and collaborative strategy, including assigning financial, preventive or curative responsibilities to actors involved.
- The input received from the stakeholders during the workshops give valuable insights for policy makers, both on the European as the national level, which are presented in Deliverable D5.8 (Hartmann et al., 2025).

There are also lessons learnt for the developed solution strategies themselves, namely:

- Some aspects can be expected to be relevant for all strategies. These include monitoring to keep track of emission sources, establishing clear regulatory threshold values for compounds, accounting for new substances with rapid legislation change and ensuring continuity in financial means for monitoring and treatment. Furthermore, it is expected that a solution strategy should always call for multiple types of solutions.
- The importance of different aspects within a strategy can vary. For example, while prevention should always be considered, it is not an overarching solution when addressing legacy pollution (i.e., pollution that is already in the environment). Similarly, the importance of curative solutions may vary depending on the situation.

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List of abbreviations

AFFF	Aqueous film forming foam
CE	Circular economy
CE route	Circular economy route
CS	Case study
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
DSF	Decision Support Framework
IED 2.0	Industrial and Livestock Rearing Emissions Directive
iPM(T)s	Industrial, Persistent, Mobile and potentially Toxic substances
JRC	Joint Research Council
PFAS	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl Substances
PM(T)s	Persistent, Mobile and potentially Toxic substances
RBF	Riverbank Filtration
RWP	Reuse Water Plant
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WWTP	Wastewater treatment plants

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Persistent, mobile, and potentially toxic (PM(T)) substances in the soil-sediment-water system present a significant barrier to the reuse of natural resources and the realization of a safe circular economy in Europe. PM(T) substances, or their degradation products, are persistent in the environment, highly soluble in water, and are therefore easily transported through the environment. Because of their physicochemical properties, PM(T) substances are poorly removed in conventional treatment processes, thereby posing a risk not only to drinking water supplies and food production, but also to the environment and ecosystem services in general (Ankley et al., 2020; Domingo & Nadal, 2019). PFAS are a well-known example of PM(T) substances.

The accumulation of PM(T) contaminants in the soil-sediment-water cycle (Figure 1) makes their removal and management crucial for the Circular Economy Action Plan. This challenge is further aggravated by inadequate analytical techniques and technical solutions. As a result, their impact extends beyond the Circular Economy Action Plan, affecting other key initiatives within the European Green Deal, such as the Zero Pollution Action Plan, Chemical Strategy for Sustainability, and the Biodiversity Strategy 2030. These interconnected challenges place significant demands on regulatory authorities, who must develop and enforce effective policies to manage these substances throughout their lifecycle, ensuring both environmental protection and alignment with broader sustainability goals.

Figure 1. PM(T) substances in the soil-sediment-water cycle across different circular economy routes.

Solutions for PM(T) substances must be environmentally sustainable, cost-effective, easily implementable, and suitable for real-life challenges. This has to be done considering the core preventive principles of the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability Action Plan. Therefore, to

successfully address the several EU ambitions and requirements, close consultation and collaboration with potential end-users is essential to generate, evaluate, and implement potential solutions.

As part of these efforts, the Horizon 2020 project PROMISCES, running from November 2021 to April 2025, aimed to address these challenges and deliver innovative solutions to overcome the impacts of PM(T) substances in the soil-sediment-water system ([PROMISCES | Home](#)). By tackling the systemic challenges caused by the specific physico-chemical properties of PM(T) substances, PROMISCES provides insights and recommendations for a healthier environment and a more sustainable use of resources, which is necessary to achieve the goal of the Green Deal and related regulations, to be the first climate-neutral continent. Within Task 5.4 of PROMISCES, a multidisciplinary approach was used to initiate the development of systemic, stakeholder-driven strategies. Central to this effort were co-creation workshops, designed to bring together diverse stakeholders in the circular economy (CE) to collaboratively identify challenges, evaluate solutions, and formulate actionable strategies.

1.2. Strategies and co-creation workshops

The scientific and technical solutions developed and optimized within PROMISCES are essential for dealing with PM(T) substances, including PFAS, in the circular economy (Narain-Ford et al., 2025). However, the effective implementation of these solutions also depends on social, economic, and regulatory frameworks. Key conditions for successful implementation include well-defined regulatory standards for solutions, clearly defined roles and responsibilities among stakeholders, and the availability of financial resources to support adoption. Without addressing these boundary conditions, advanced scientific and technical solutions may fall short of achieving a safe and sustainable circular economy. To ensure these boundary conditions are integrated into the design and implementation of solutions, a systemic view is required – one that also considers the social, economic and regulatory framework.

The specific boundary conditions within this systemic view must be informed by diverse groups of stakeholders who can contribute with their insights and expertise. Within PROMISCES, this was achieved through the organization of co-creation workshops, which had the following objectives (see chapter 3 for more details):

- Bring together stakeholders from various disciplines to explore challenges regarding PM(T)s, including PFAS
- Identify potential solutions for these challenges
- Evaluate the conditions necessary for their success
- Reflect on what actions the participating stakeholders, both as individuals and institutions, could take to implement the proposed solutions.

Organized around three case studies representing three different circular economy routes, the co-creation workshops provided input for the strategy module of the [Decision Support Framework \(DSF\) for risk management of PM\(T\) substances in a circular economy](#) developed in PROMISCES. Additionally, the outcomes of these workshops, along with other inputs, were used to formulate policy recommendations for effective management of PM(T) substances, including PFAS. A special effort was made to address the aligned implementation of relevant EU directives, strategies and action plans, including, but not limited to the Water Framework Directive (WFD; 2000/60/EC), the Drinking Water Directive (EU 2020/2184), the Sewage Sludge Directive (86/278/EEC), Industrial and Livestock Rearing Emissions Directive (IED 2.0; EU 2024/1785), the Chemicals Strategy for

Sustainability, the Zero Pollution Action Plan, and the Circular Economy Action Plan. The policy recommendations will be presented in Deliverable D5.8 (Hartmann et al., 2025), expected in March 2025.

1.3.PROMISCES objectives and deliverable outline

PROMISCES organised three workshops, focusing on three circular economy routes: A) a semi-closed water cycle for drinking water supply (CS2); B) wastewater reuse for agricultural irrigation (CS3); and C) nutrient and energy recovery from treated sludge for use in fertilisers (CS4). For CS2, a second follow-up workshop was organized, bringing the total number of organized workshops to four. Case study 2 and case study 3 focussed solely on PFAS substances, while case study 3 included other industrial PM(T) substances. This distinction between PFAS and other industrial PM(T) substances was made, because when compiling the PROMISCES target list at the start of the project not all PFAS monitored in the PROMISCES case studies were known PM(T) substances.

By combining scientific and technological solutions with stakeholder-driven strategies, PROMISCES promotes a holistic approach to achieving a circular economy in line with the non-toxic environment ambition and safe reuse of resources. The co-creation process integrated perspectives from diverse disciplines, including research and academia, authorities, operators, solution providers, and civil society . Outcomes of the co-creation processes are provided in Chapter 3 in blue call-out boxes as examples. A more detailed description of the outcomes can be found in [Deliverable D5.4](#) (Narain-Ford et al., 2025) while the output summaries are provided in Annex C, D, and E.

Co-creation is a well-known methodology generally employed to bring multiple stakeholders to the table to participate in an innovation process, ensuring buy-in from all partners involved. There are multiple articles and publications that provide guidance on using co-creation in different subject matter areas (European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation et al., 2023; USAID, 2024). Notably, the Joint Research Commission (JRC) published a handbook to help users to effectively use co-creation to develop policies, by outlining steps needed and providing recommendations to engage stakeholders in participatory processes (Matti et al., 2022).

The JRC Handbook and other guidance documents can be used as resources on generally organizing co-creation processes to inform policy. In our PROMISCES project, co-creation also proved to be a valuable tool for addressing the multi-faceted nature of PM(T), including PFAS. In this Deliverable D5.6, we used the experience and lessons learnt in the co-creation workshops organized within the project, to provide specific guidance on how to co-create a solution strategy for dealing with PM(T) substances, including PFAS, in a circular economy.

Chapter 2 presents the conceptual framework of solution strategies and co-creation and highlights the methodology used to select the case studies. Chapter 3 focusses on the co-creation process itself, outlining tools and tips for carrying it out. In Chapter 4, the lessons learnt from the workshops are discussed. In Chapter 5, we provide key takeaways on organising co-creation processes and developing the outputs into solution strategies.

2. Theory on solution strategies

2.1. Solution strategy

The final goal of a solution strategy is to enable reaching a zero-pollution or non-toxic environment and safe reuse of resources. Here, we provide a short description of the important elements within a solution strategy, which are shown in Figure 2. Four types of systematic solutions are considered, i.e. solutions related to prevention, treatment, monitoring and risk assessment. They are interconnected in multiple ways and described in [Deliverable D5.4](#) (Narain-Ford et al., 2025). Boundary conditions such as the regulatory framework, financial support, or social perspectives (see also Figure 3) are important for the implementation of the four solution types.

Figure 2. Systemic view of the types of systematic solutions in the DSF.

A solution strategy can consist of monitoring measures to characterise and quantify the PM(T) substances within a circular economy route. This can include a strategy for determining how and where monitoring should take place. Another solution type involves the assessment of risks associated to the PM(T) substances likely to be present in the circular economy route and their hazardous properties, based on existing monitoring data and other available information. A solution strategy will then consider the direct solutions that can be applied to remove PM(T) substances, therefore enabling a circular economy. Such direct solutions can consist of curative measures, such as treatment, and preventive measures, such as substitution. The framework of scientific and technical elements to consider in a solution strategy was developed in PROMISCES Deliverable D5.4 (Narain-Ford et al., 2025). Finally, it is necessary to identify the boundary conditions that should be fulfilled for the successful implementation of solutions. During a co-creation process, the role of boundary conditions within a solution strategy is crucial and can vary based on local conditions. The same applies to the feasibility and role of direct systematic solutions (prevention, monitoring, risk assessment and treatment). Therefore, it is often more effective to develop a strategy tailored to a

specific local situation or circular economy route, rather than focusing on individual PM(T) substances. The following aspects pertaining to boundary conditions may be relevant (Figure 33):

- public health, for example health effects/safety of the circular product;
- environmental health, for example effects on the environment;
- financial aspects, for example a high cost of PFAS removal in wastewater treatment;
- regulatory aspects, for example establishing threshold values to be reached;
- social aspects, for example the lack of knowledge on PM(T)s, and
- technical aspects, for example removal efficiency.

Figure 3. The multi-disciplinary aspects considered important for a solution strategy.

These aspects need to be defined with local stakeholders from different backgrounds to account for both the multidisciplinary boundary conditions that should be fulfilled, and the relevant local conditions and trade-offs. By using a co-creation approach, perspectives from diverse disciplines can be integrated, including from PM(T) experts, civil society, solution providers and government representatives. This collaboration ensures that the strategies developed can address systemic challenges holistically. The inclusion of stakeholders outside the PM(T) domain, such as experts on non-chemical solutions for societal functions, provides valuable insights into innovative approaches. This ensures that the co-created solutions are both feasible and broadly applicable.

2.2. Co-creation framework based on the Delphi method

The Delphi method is a helpful framework that can be used for developing the structure of a co-creation process. This method consists of multiple iterative phases of discussion to gain consensus (Dalkey & Helmer, 1963). At the start of each new phase, the findings from the previous phase are summarized and presented to the stakeholders. This method allows for structured and interactive input, ensuring a robust knowledge basis and diverse stakeholder perspectives inform each phase. Elements from the Delphi method can be incorporated to give a structure to the co-creation process.

Concretely, the process can be structured into three iterative phases, designed to build upon each other and refine the development of strategies through continuous stakeholder input:

- **Phase 1. Problem definition:** The initial phase aims to define and explore the problem of PM(T) substances within a circular economy route from a system perspective (whole PM(T) life cycle) based on the perceptions of the stakeholders of the problems. This also includes identifying barriers or trade-offs that must be addressed within a solution strategy. Relevant questions include: Do we have a sufficiently clear picture of the system and its specific stakeholder roles and involvement to build scenarios for possible directions of future problem solving?
- **Phase 2. Solution finding:** Building on Phase 1, this phase focusses on problem solving. The stakeholders evaluate potential solutions derived from existing research and the input of the stakeholders. Additionally, this phase focusses on non-direct actions that need to be taken to ensure boundary conditions are fulfilled. The stakeholders are also challenged to prioritize solutions and actions. Relevant questions include: Are there more solutions? How realistic are these solutions given the social and financial contexts? What can we expect from different solutions?
- **Phase 3. Strategy building:** The final phase builds upon the previous two phases and focusses on building the solution strategy on how to reach a safe circular reuse of resources and a non-toxic environment. The solution strategy consists of direct solutions to reduce PM(T) substances and actions to create the necessary boundary conditions. The feasibility of these solutions and actions is also part of the strategy. Additionally, actions that need to be taken can be further specified, by letting the stakeholders formulate actions for themselves.

In Box 1, the concretization of the different Delphi method phases in the PROMISCES workshops is presented. In the following section (Section 2.3), the selection and the topics of the case studies are explained and Chapter 3 then explains the separate parts of the workshops in more detail.

Box 1 – Delphi method within the PROMISCES co-creation workshops

Within PROMISCES, the separate phases from the Delphi methodology are translated to separate phases within the local co-creation workshops. In , the corresponding phases of the Delphi method with the PROMISCES local co-creation workshops are given.

In the PROMISCES workshops, an extra part 0 was introduced, which served as an introduction of the participants, and to establish a common goal within the workshop. Additionally, phase 1 of the Delphi method was concretized into two parts, one part focusing on establishing a common view on the problem of PM(T)s within the circular economy route, and the other part on defining the multidisciplinary barriers related to the boundary conditions. Lastly, a presentation of the research from the PROMISCES project was included as a bridge between the first phase on problem defining and the second phase of problem solving.

Table 1. The corresponding phases of the Delphi method phases with the PROMISCES local co-creation workshops.

Delphi Method Phase	Respective Co-Creation Workshop Part
	Part 0: Introduction / Bringing together
Phase 1: Problem definition	Part 1: Exploring the problem Part 2: Barriers and enablers
	<i>Presentation of the PROMISCES case study results as a bridge towards solutions</i>
Phase 2: Solution finding	Part 3: Identifying and prioritizing solutions
Phase 3: Strategy building	Part 4: Constructing a strategy

2.3. Solution strategy cases

Solution strategies can be made for specific PM(T)-use cases. This line was followed in the [PROMISCES Deliverable D5.4](#), where solutions for five example PM(T) substances are given (Narain-Ford et al., 2025). Within PROMISCES, the targeted PM(T)s for each case study are presented in Figure 4. A classification of all substances included in the target list of the PROMISCES project is available in [Deliverable D5.1](#) (Sardi, 2024).

Figure 4. Number of PFAS and other iPM(T) i.e. industrial substances monitored through target screening in the 7 case studies (CS). Note that some substances are repeated across different case studies.

As explained in Section 2.1, local conditions and local context are critical for developing a solution strategy, especially when determining which indirect actions, i.e. boundary conditions, need to be fulfilled. Therefore, it is often more effective to develop a strategy tailored to a specific local situation or circular economy route, rather than focusing on individual PM(T) substances. Many of the solutions and actions that are presented in such a local solution strategy are broadly applicable to multiple PM(T) substances.

A tailored solution strategy can be developed for each case where achieving circularity is the goal. Before initiating a co-creation process, it is essential to assess to which extent the two recommended criteria listed below are fulfilled:

- Required and relevant stakeholders should be available and contactable.
- It should be possible to discuss the case study openly, without confidentiality constraints, including data sharing possibilities.

In PROMISCES, the selection criteria above were used for identifying suitable case studies for co-creation workshops. First, all case study (CS) leaders were consulted during the consortium meeting in Vienna in July 2022. This consultation included a series of questions assessing the suitability and feasibility of co-hosting one or more workshops with local stakeholders. The case study leaders' knowledge of relevant local stakeholders and the ability to reach them were key criteria in selecting the case studies for the co-creation process. Co-hosting entails not only managing the logistics of the event but also actively engaging stakeholders, sharing relevant data, and reflecting on the results of the case studies. The local partners must also be able to share details of their research, which is not possible if the research is confidential. An additional requirement was that the case study should comprehensively cover the soil-water-sediment system and broadly address different circular economy routes.

Several limitations regarding the case studies for co-creation workshops emerged. Case studies CS1, CS5, and CS6 indicated that their overview of relevant stakeholders was not fully complete, while CS7 was unable to share results with stakeholders due to confidentiality constraints. Consequently, only three case studies were deemed suitable for co-hosting and participating in the co-creation workshops (CS2, CS3 and CS4). These case studies represented diverse circular economy routes while

allowing actionable and context-specific discussions. An overview of the selected case studies is presented in Table 2. Boxes 2, 3 and 4 provide a description of each selected case study¹. For CS2, a second follow-up workshop was organized, bringing the total number of organized workshops to four. The results of the case study co-creation processes are summarized in Chapter 3, providing real-life examples to illustrate each stage of the co-creation process. The complete outcomes of the co-creation processes can be found in [Deliverable D5.4](#) (Narain-Ford et al., 2025) and in the output summaries (Annex C, D, E).

Table 2. Overview of all PROMISCES’ case studies and those deemed suitable for one or more co-creation workshops.

Case Study #	Title	Suitable for co-creation (Yes/No)
1	PFAS and PM(T) fate and remediation in the semi-closed urban water cycle – Berlin (Germany)	N
2	Sources, pathways, fate and transport of PFAS in the Upper Danube basin - (Austria, and Hungary)	Y
3	Water reuse from a wastewater treatment plant with a high share of industrial wastewater for agricultural irrigation – Barcelona Province (Catalonia)	Y
4	Landfill leachate treatment to safe resource recovery from wastewater treatment plants – Ancona (Italy) and Sofia (Bulgaria)	Y
5	Removal of PFAS from dredged sediments for material recycling – Ancona (Italy)	N
6	PFAS Fate and transport and remediation in soil and groundwater contaminated by AFFF – Orléans (France)	N
7	Remediation of groundwater contaminated in a fire-fighting training site - Barcelona Province (Catalonia)	N

¹ More information on the case studies is available at <https://promisces.eu/Project/Case+Studies.html>

Box 2 – CS2 description

Along the Danube River, there are multiple locations where water is abstracted for potable use, via riverbank filtration (RBF). However, the chemical water quality of the Danube River is influenced by various discharges from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) and stormwater from an area with more than 80 million inhabitants throughout 14 countries. The largest contributors to river pollution are the discharges from WWTPs, which introduce a range of persistent, mobile, and toxic (PM(T)) substances like PFAS into the water, some of which are hardly removed via the RBF. Another important consideration is the legacy contamination within the system. Legacy contamination can have lasting effects on PM(T) concentrations within the Danube, even if emissions from WWTPs and industries along the river are greatly reduced or eliminated.

Unfortunately, there is a lack of knowledge about PM(T) substances in the river and how these chemicals impact the drinking water abstracted via bank filtration along the river. Within the PROMISCES case study, PM(T) substances, especially PFAS, within the Danube River and RBF systems are studied. The case study focusses mostly on monitoring and identifying potential sources. Outcomes of the research can be found in deliverables D2.3 (Groot et al., 2025) and D2.4 (Zessner et al., 2025).

Box 3 – CS3 description

The Catalan Water Agency (ACA: Agència Catalana de l'Aigua) seeks to promote water reuse in the Besòs River Basin to mitigate water restrictions put in place due to recent periods of severe droughts (2022-2024), to combat the growing water scarcity. To this end, 64 municipalities working together in the Consorci Besòs Tordera (CBT) initiated the Reclaimed Water Master Plan (RWMP). This plan involves the construction of a number of Reuse Water Plants (RWPs) and transportation infrastructure to meet urban, agricultural, industrial and environmental water demands. However, in the current design of the RWPs, removing PM(T) substances is not considered. This might be needed if the water is to be used for agricultural purposes (irrigation) to prevent that the PM(T) concentrations found in crops exceed human and environmental safety levels.

The PROMISCES research focusses on a hybrid treatment combining e-Peroxone (ozonation and electrochemical oxidation) followed by a nature-based post-treatment. Additionally, the transfer of contaminants from reclaimed water to crops will be evaluated, and the risk to human health from direct consumption (crops) and indirect consumption (fodder for cattle) will be quantified. Outcomes of the research can be found in the PROMISCES deliverable D4.3 (Mejjide Fernández et al., 2025).

Box 4 – CS4 description

In Italy and Bulgaria currently, conventional leachate treatment plants are not designed to remove emerging organic micropollutants, such as perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), which can be persistent, mobile and toxic (PM(T)) for the environment. Generally, in Italy landfill leachate treatment plants discharge treated landfill leachate in municipal wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). Hence, landfill leachate may be a major source of municipal wastewater contamination by PFAS and PM(T) substances. In Bulgaria, the existing landfills either treat leachate locally and discharge it to a water body or dry gully; or recirculate it back onto the landfill.

Within the PROMISCES project, the advanced treatments reverse osmosis or nanofiltration are studied to remove PM(T) substances. Additionally, innovative and more sustainable technologies have been tested to treat sludge and concentrate coming from landfill leachate treatments, which are pyrolysis and plasma. Outcomes of the research can be found in the PROMISCES deliverables D3.3 (Lancioni, Blumenthal, Sgroi, Fatone, Frugis, et al., 2024), D3.4 (Institut de Physique du Globe de Paris (IPGP), 2025), D4.5 (Lancioni, Blumenthal, Sgroi, Fatone, Lazzazzara, et al., 2024) and D4.6 (UNISOFIA, 2025).

3. Organizing co-creation for solution strategies

In PROMISCES, we organised four co-creation workshops surrounding the three selected case studies (see Section 2.3), with one case study (CS3) including an additional follow-up workshop, which was held online. This chapter guides the reader through the various steps of the co-creation process, offering concrete examples and providing guidance for future efforts in organising co-creation workshops.

3.1. Setting the scene

3.1.1 Understanding the case / problem statement

To create a solution strategy, the co-creation process needs to be rooted in the local situation surrounding the case study to appropriately identify barriers or challenges to address PM(T)s in the soil-water-sediment system. The local situation includes aspects such as the current regulatory context at national and European levels, ongoing discussions or strategies being developed in the country/region, and relevant public perspectives. For this, a description of the case study focusing on the circular economy route, the known presence and sources of PM(T)s, potential solutions to deal with PM(T)s, and related challenges or issues related to it can be made.

This initial problem definition can be used to motivate stakeholders to partake in the process by defining the relevance of the workshop for the current situation and highlighting the role that stakeholders can play in addressing these open questions, thereby moving the needle on strategies to address PM(T)s.

The problem definition should be confirmed and adjusted with the co-creation stakeholders before further discussions occur. This ensures that all participants understand the ‘system’ and the focus of the co-creation process similarly and can thus contribute appropriately to the discussion. One way to acquire their perspectives is through a preliminary stakeholder survey.

In the PROMISCES workshops, the initial problem definition was done through discussions with the case study leaders. In addition to the aforementioned aspects of the local situation, the problem definition also included the solutions offered by the case study and a description of the specific aspects of the problem addressed by these solutions. Additionally, we collaborated with the case study leaders to address any outstanding questions regarding the implementation of their scientific and technical solutions. This dialogue aimed to establish a preliminary direction for the co-creation process (see Box 5).

To gather the initial perspectives of the stakeholders, an online survey was sent to all registered participants before the start of the workshop. The full questionnaire from CS3 can be found in Annex A, and a few examples of the questions and responses are provided in Figure 5 and Figure 6.

Figure 5. Survey responses from stakeholders involved in the CS3 co-creation process, where they were asked to rank their level of concern about PM(T) substances in water resources generally and in reclaimed water for crop irrigation.

Figure 6. Survey responses from stakeholders involved in the CS3 co-creation process, where they were asked to what extent they agree with the statements about the removal of PM(T) substances from reclaimed water for crop irrigation.

The survey responses can be presented back to the stakeholders during the co-creation workshop. These responses can be used to engage the stakeholders during the problem definition, further identify important topics that a strategy should address, and define the direction of the overall co-creation process. Additionally, it can be used as a starting point for the discussion within the co-creation workshop, although adjustments by stakeholders during the workshop are of course possible.

Box 5 – CS3 Co-Creation Problem Statement

Current Situation

The Catalan Water Agency (ACA) aims to enhance water reuse in the Besòs River Basin to address severe drought-related water restrictions. The Consorci Besòs Tordera (CBT), representing 64 municipalities, launched the Reclaimed Water Master Plan (RWMP) to build Reclaimed Water Plants (RWPs) and infrastructure for urban, agricultural, industrial, and environmental needs. In 2022, 95% of the basin's water came from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs), with potential for reuse in agricultural irrigation to reduce drinking water consumption. However, emerging contaminants, including persistent (P), mobile (M), and toxic (T) substances, must be removed to ensure safety. Conventional treatment methods used in RWPs do not address PM(T) removal, but future regulations may require it to protect human and environmental health for water reuse.

Addressing PM(T) Risks

In CS3, the Montornès del Vallès WWTP is testing hybrid technologies, such as Electrochemical Advanced Oxidation Processes (EAOP) combined with wetlands, to remove industrial contaminants and produce reclaimed water suitable for agricultural irrigation. Risk assessments are being conducted to establish pollutant thresholds and guide crop selection and farming best practices to minimize contaminant transfer to edible parts. Engaging local and national stakeholders is vital to align perspectives and support the construction of RWP and reclaimed water use in the region.

3.1.2 Defining objectives

Using the case studies and the Delphi method (see Chapter 2), we formulated four main objectives for the co-creation process. For this, we used questions such as “what does it mean to create a “solution strategy to reach a non-toxic environment and the safe reuse of resources?”, and “how does this align with the case study and its local context and stakeholders?”. While the objectives formulated below are general enough to apply to each case study, they were updated during each co-creation process to accommodate the specific case study context. The objectives, which correspond to separate parts of the workshop (see Box 1), were to:

- Discuss the problem statement and local context (see Section 3.1.1)
- Identify barriers, trade-offs and other factors that need to be addressed to support the development of a solution strategy (see Section 3.4.2)
- Define solutions to overcome these barriers (see Section 3.4.4)
- Co-create an interdisciplinary, system-wide strategy that incorporates the defined solutions and needed actors (see Section 3.4.5)

Using the formulated objectives, the format, methods, and desired outcomes of the co-creation process can be defined.

3.2. Stakeholder identification

3.2.1 Mapping relevant sectors

The core idea of co-creation is to include perspectives from multiple stakeholders. The case study leaders' knowledge of relevant local stakeholders and their ability to reach them were used as key metrics in selecting the case studies to participate in the co-creation process (see Section 2.3). This is in line with the recommendations from the EC report (European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation et al., 2023), which mentions that stakeholder selection should be based on capacities, availability, and representation of different target groups, and should include those that are usually not involved in such discussions. Co-creation of solution strategies for PM(T)s and PFAS should ideally involve stakeholders along the entire circularity route (Table 3).

Table 3. Relevant stakeholder groups that deal with PMT(s) within a circular economy.

Stakeholder Group	Group Composition	Relevance for Solution Strategies
Research / Academia	Universities, research institutes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop technological solutions to address PM(T)s • Provide subject-matter expertise and perspective
Regulator / Authority (national, regional, local)	Government agencies/ministries (environment, water, public health), city councils	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Influence or make policy and legislation • Promote or support uptake of technological solutions • Issue permits, certificates • Responsible for ensuring compliance with relevant regulations
Operators	Wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) operators, drinking water treatment plant operators, landfill operators & utility associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can implement the proposed technological solution • Responsible for complying with relevant regulations
Solution Providers	Technology developers, consultants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop technological solutions to address PM(T)s • Provide subject-matter expertise and perspective
Industry	Producers of chemicals, emitters, water users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offer opportunities to implement developed solutions • Responsible for complying with relevant regulations
Final Customers	E.g. farmers for agricultural reuse or golf clubs for non-potable reuse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Require certain quality of water and sludge • Aid in the realization of circular economy routes
Civil Society	Citizens, end-users, mass media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Influence social pressure on regulators to address PM(T)s • Provide public perception support for successful implementation of solutions • Important target audience to expand communication outreach

Table 3 represents an overview of mapping relevant stakeholders, but does not indicate actual representation of these relevant stakeholders. There are many challenges associated with winning

the participation of a representative group of stakeholders, which are further touched upon in the following section (Section 3.2.2). To ensure a multi-perspective nature during the co-creation processes themselves, those stakeholders who are present can be asked to consider the perspectives of any missing (non-present) sectors. Of course, the exact list of which stakeholders are most relevant depends on the focus of the specific co-creation process.

4 lists the stakeholder sectors included in the three co-creation processes of the PROMISCES project as well as those missing from the co-creation process but considered relevant. For the three case studies, the size of the co-creation workshops varied greatly, as did the distribution of participants among the sectors (Figure 7). Analysed together, Table 4 and Figure 7 demonstrate the variance in invited stakeholders versus present stakeholders, signalling the need for effective stakeholder engagement.

Table 4. Stakeholder sectors present in the co-creation workshop or identified explicitly as missing/desired by workshop participants (in parentheses).

Case Study	Stakeholder Sectors for Co-Creation
CS2: Semi-closed drinking water cycle in the Danube River Basin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research / Academia • Solution Providers • Operators: Drinking water treatment plant operators, utility associations • Regulator / Authority: Water • (Industry / Producers of chemicals)
CS3: Agricultural reuse in the Besòs River Region	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research / Academia • Operators: WWTP operators, drinking water treatment plant operators • Regulator / Authority: Regional environmental authority, regional water authority • Solution Providers • Final Customers: Agricultural, golf club organization • (Regulator / Authority: National/regional public health authority)
CS4: Landfill leachate management in the Marche & Lazio Regions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operators: Water utility, waste & landfill • Regulator / Authority: National public health authority, National environmental authority • Solution Providers • Research / Academia

Figure 7. Distribution of workshop participants among sectors for the three co-creation processes for CSs 2,3 and 4.

3.2.2 Stakeholder engagement & participation

As briefly mentioned in the previous section, securing stakeholder engagement is a challenging component of organising co-creation processes. Nevertheless, there are a few methods that can easily be implemented to engage with stakeholders and encourage their participation, such as personalised outreach and incentives for participation.

Since the case studies involved in the co-creation process were selected based on their access to local, relevant stakeholders, it was possible in most instances to individually contact stakeholders to ask them for their participation. Such personalised outreach has higher chances of success than sending out “cold e-mails”, or e-mails with no prior contact. This demonstrates the importance of stakeholder mapping.

Additionally, contextualising the co-creation process in the current local situation and developing topics relevant for stakeholders is fundamental to securing their participation. Taking part in the co-creation workshop requires a sense of commitment to: 1) take time off from work and 2) actively engage in the process. This commitment should be kept in mind while planning the co-creation process. To help secure stakeholder participation, it is important to define the added value of participation from the stakeholder perspective. By participating in the solution strategy co-creation process, stakeholders could expect to:

- Play an active role in the development of a CE route-specific strategy;
- Receive the latest developments from the case study research partners on innovative solutions;
- Discuss current barriers and enablers for the implementation of the specific CE route;
- Network with other local stakeholders within the same circular system.

Formulating and designing stakeholder outreach is an important step in the co-creation process. In the “Innovation camp methodology handbook”, Rissola et al. (2017) provides examples on how to inform and involve participants in Annexes 11 and 12 (What You Can Expect as Participant, Example of Information for Participants). For the PROMISCES co-creation processes, we shared this information with desired stakeholders via unique webpages on the PROMISCES website (see Box 6).

There is no ideal number of participants for co-creation, as the main focus should be on organising an inclusive process, where all key stakeholder sectors are represented as well as stakeholders with different levels of decision-making power (Matti et al., 2022). The Co-Creation for Policy Methodology (2022) states that co-creation can include small processes (6-10 people) or very large (more than 500). The PROMISCES co-creation workshops were attended by approximately 10-30 participants each.

Box 67 – Co-Creation Process Website

The PROMISCES team created a webpage for each of the three co-creation processes, using this webpage as the main source of information for invited stakeholders, for both before and after the co-creation process. Before the co-creation process, the webpages explained the problem statement behind the workshop (see Section 3.1.1), clearly laid out the objectives (see Section 3.1.2), and formulated the added value for stakeholders in participating in the workshop (see Section 3.2.2). The webpages also provided logistical information, such as the location and agenda.

Figure 8. Screenshot of the webpage created for the CS2 co-creation process, which took place online. This serves as an example for stakeholder outreach.

3.2.3 Informed consent

Informed consent is a critical aspect of ethical stakeholder engagement in co-creation processes. It ensures that participants are fully aware of the purpose, scope, and use of their contributions, while safeguarding their privacy and autonomy. To uphold these principles, the following guidelines should be followed to create a transparent, respectful, and inclusive environment for all participants:

- Ensure that the stakeholders are aware they are joining the workshops on a voluntary basis and may choose to withdraw at any time.
- Clearly inform the participants that the output of the co-creation workshops will only be used for specified purposes, i.e. for co-creating solution strategies and, in the case of PROMISCES, contributing public deliverables within the context of the project, namely this deliverable, [Deliverable D5.4](#) (Narain-Ford et al., 2025) and Deliverable D5.8 (Hartmann et al., 2025). The outcomes should also be summarized and shared with the participants. The output summaries of the PROMISCES workshops communicated with the participants are found in Annex C, D and E.

- To protect individual privacy, opinions, questions or remarks expressed within the workshops should be made anonymized, ensuring they are untraceable to individual stakeholders.
- Inform the co-hosts and participants that results, information or data shared during the workshops should generally be open and free to be used by the other participants.
- Inclusivity is a priority, and positions of stakeholders that do not comply with the majority consensus should be acknowledged as well as documented in the output summary. Further, to achieve a broadly accepted solution strategy, it is important to be aware of any viewpoints not explicitly represented within the workshop.
- Photos taken during the workshop should not show individual participants.

3.3. Co-creation organisation

One important aspect to increase the likelihood of participation is to organize the co-creation process around the needs of the stakeholders. Specifically, the location and language play an important role. If the case study and the stakeholders are local to a specific region and if the stakeholders are known contacts (i.e. not cold calls), an onsite co-creation workshop is more suitable. This allows the stakeholders to network with one another more easily and is beneficial for the co-creation process by creating a common space to work towards a shared goal. However, if the stakeholders are geographically dispersed, as was the case for CS2 which targets the Danube River Basin, or if they are not personally known by the case study leaders, then an online workshop may be easier to organize. An online workshop limits the necessary travel time and generally lowers the barriers to participation for stakeholders who may not feel as personally tied to the co-creation objectives. For the PROMISCES CS2 workshop, the first attempt was an in-person workshop, but this changed when it became apparent that stakeholders were more likely to join an online workshop. Table 5 describes the format of each of the three co-creation processes conducted in PROMISCES.

As explained in the table, the CS3 co-creation process was divided into two workshops – one onsite and one online. This showcases the possibility of mixing formats during the co-creation process itself in order to better accommodate stakeholder needs and desires. In this instance, a second workshop was planned to allow stakeholders time to pull together the identified barriers and solutions into a comprehensive strategy, and stakeholders expressed the desire to meet online, so as to make participation easier. Section 3.4.6 explains how onsite co-creation methods were translated to an online environment.

The language of the workshop should be determined similarly. The predominant language used by the stakeholders for their work relating to the CE route should ideally be chosen as the co-creation language. This helps ensure that participation is active, creative and constructive and links the developed solution to the local context. However, if the stakeholders are distributed, a common language should be chosen, which may hinder the participation of local stakeholders. This underlines the importance of understanding the local context and stakeholders before planning the co-creation process.

Table 5. Workshop format and language for the three PROMISCES co-creation processes.

Case Study	Workshop Format	Workshop Language
CS2	Online via zoom	English
CS3	Onsite (Delphi phases 1-2), online (Delphi phase 3))	Catalan
CS4	Onsite	Italian (written materials in English)

3.4. Co-creation methods and tools

3.4.1 Goal setting

The participatory nature of co-creation makes it important that stakeholders feel comfortable and empowered in bringing their own perspectives and ideas to the discussion. One way to create a comfortable, collaborative atmosphere is to ask the participants to establish a common goal for the co-creation process. This ensures all participants are on the same page and agree on the desired end result, and it is an easy first step to get the participants comfortable with speaking in the group. It is important to note that the goal defined by the participants may not necessarily align with the objectives and problem statement defined earlier in the process by the organizers and case study leaders. The stakeholders are the ones active within the circular economy route and may therefore have needs that differ from those of the case study. Additionally, the stakeholders can have personal goals for the workshop, such as gaining more insight into potential solutions. This is part of the process, and the co-creation methods are meant to be flexible to account for the specific desires of the participants.

Within the case study workshops, the PROMISCES research provided insights into the problem definition and the potential scientific and technical solutions. The goal of the specific workshops changed according to the local conditions and was discussed with the case study leads and the stakeholders. For example, in the CS3 workshop, each participant was asked to state their desired goal of the workshop and each point written down on a flipchart. After each participant had a chance, the individual goals were clustered and summarised by the moderator, with the help of the stakeholders, into one common goal (see Box 7).

Box 7 8– Participant Defined Goal for the Besòs River Region Workshop (CS2)

- Share knowledge among stakeholders
- Identify barriers and accompanying solutions for wastewater reuse
- Establish quality criteria for reclaimed water
- Develop an immediate, concrete action plan

This goal should be referred to throughout the co-creation process to ensure the stakeholders provide feedback in line with the end objective. It is also a way to check-in after each phase of the workshop to assess the progress made.

3.4.2 Barrier & enabler identification

Systemic barriers associated with PM(T) substances hinder the implementation of circular economy routes. The existence of such barriers or trade-offs pre-empts the need for a solution strategy and dictates the actions that need to be taken, which is why the identification of barriers or trade-offs should be the first main step in a co-creation process to create a zero-pollution strategy. Barriers that prevent the implementation of a circular economy route span the entire value chain, much like the involved stakeholders, and can be categorized into several factors (see Figure 33 from Chapter 2):

1. **Technical barriers or trade-offs:** Pertaining to technological needs and the availability of qualified workers, best practices, state-of-the-art technology, such as lack of scalable alternatives or insufficient knowledge transfer.
2. **Environmental barriers or trade-offs:** Pertaining to the unintended environmental impacts of proposed solutions, including (but not limited to) potential emissions or by-products of PFAS and other industrial PM(T) degradation.
3. **Public health barriers or trade-offs:** Pertaining to risks and uncertainties about human exposure, toxicity of PFAS and other industrial PM(T) alternatives, and ensuring solutions do not inadvertently harm communities or workers involved in the value chain.
4. **Social barriers or trade-offs:** Pertaining to public awareness, acceptance, and trust, including resistance to behavioural changes, scepticism toward new technologies, or disparities in stakeholder engagement and representation. Such social barriers or trade-offs can be regionally variable.
5. **Financial barriers or trade-offs:** Pertaining to the cost of implementing circular solutions, such as high initial investments or limited funding or incentives.
6. **Legislative/regulatory barriers or trade-offs:** Pertaining to gaps, inconsistencies, or delays in regulations, such as unclear limits for PFAS and other industrial PM(T), lack of harmonization across directives, or insufficient enforcement of pollution controls.

It is important to note here that barriers or trade-offs may span several categories, and the distinction often depends on the stakeholders' perceptions. For example, a barrier such as the generation of by-products during treatment could be considered as a technical barrier, as it pertains to the available technologies and processes, or it could be considered as an environmental barrier, as these by-products then enter the environment, or as a public health barrier, as the toxicity of these by-products may be unknown. The exact categorization of barriers or trade-offs is not what is important in such a co-creation process. The six categories serve to jumpstart the brainstorming process and to ensure that the entire circular economy route is being considered.

Often, there are not only aspects hindering the implementation of a circular economy route, but there may be structures, supporting services or societal pressure that facilitate the route. These aspects, known as enablers, are also important to identify, as they can often lead to or enhance solutions that address barriers. Enablers can also be classified into the same six categories.

In a co-creation process, it is important to allow participants the chance to contribute all the barriers or enablers that they encounter in their work. This is because we want a solution strategy to be as comprehensive as possible and address challenges that occur along the entire chain. One method that allows for this collection of inputs, is the method of world cafés. World cafés encourage informal discussions and idea-sharing, fostering collaboration and innovative problem-solving among diverse participants. Participants are split into equal-sized groups and given 5-10 minutes at a table that focused on two categories of barriers/enablers. With the help of a local moderator, stakeholders listed relevant barriers and enablers for those two categories, and then switched to the next table, which also met for 5-10 minutes. At the start of each new group, the moderator explains the

barriers/enablers that have been identified previously, giving stakeholders the chance to add to the list.

At the end of the world café activity in the PROMISCES workshops, each moderator of the three world café groups had the chance to present the final list of barriers and enablers for their respective two categories (i.e. technical, financial). This served as a type of feedback round with the participants, as it gave them the chance to review the final lists and identify any remaining aspects to be listed.

3.4.3 Barrier prioritization

Of course, it is impossible to address all barriers with a single solution strategy ; some barriers may be more important to address first . Therefore, the next step in the co-creation process should be to prioritize the identified barriers that should be tackled within a solution strategy first. Again, here, it is also important to gather feedback from all participating stakeholders to ensure that the perspectives of various roles – researchers, administrators, water operators, etc. – are represented in the future strategy.

In the PROMISCES co-creation process, participants were each given one red, yellow and green sticker, with which they could vote for different barriers. Red represented the highest priority, yellow medium priority, and green lower priority. The barriers with the most red stickers, or a combination of all three colours, were selected as priority barriers (Figure Annex-B5).

The co-creation moderators should review the barriers to create a new list of the prioritized barriers, which will be used in the next part of the process to suggest solutions. One way to do this is to encircle the barriers with the most stickers and rephrase them into a new list of prioritized barriers (Figure 6). The barriers that were identified as having higher priority for all three co-creation processes can be seen in Boxes 8, 9, 10.

Box 9 – Prioritized barriers for CS2 (semi-closed drinking water cycle)

Category	Barrier
Technical	Difficult substance properties for removal & destruction
	Information barrier: which PFAS to measure? Which are important? Which methods? What is their price? What is the removal rate?
Technical / Environmental	Treatment techniques can be detrimental to the environment (energy intensive) - priority / balance of what is more important?
	Legacy pollution (Diverse presence in nature - long lasting supply from the environments)
Social	High societal request of products that contain PM(T) substances
Financial	Costs of treatment methods (financial and energy); not all countries are able to afford tertiary/quaternary treatment.
Legislative	Legislation is always lacking behind on advances of research and/or the creation of new chemicals
	Balancing regulation between protection and economic interest for production & use

Box 10 – Prioritized barriers for CS3 (agricultural reuse of water)

Category	Barrier
Technical	Generation of by-products (concentrates, oxidation, etc.). Lack of knowledge about the by-products of Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOP)
Technical / Financial	The cost of treatment technology is not always clear or comparable.
Financial / Social	Lack of funding
	Cost of water
Social / Public Health	Lack of knowledge about the risk to public health
	Perception (and communication) of PM(T)s to the general public. Lack of knowledge and the presence of misinformation
Public Health / Governance	The current organization of the administration (reclaimed water, drinking water, and public health). Who is responsible?
Public Health / Legislative	Lack of a specific list of PM(T)s or indicators, with quality limits. Current legislation does not consider PM(T) substances.

Box 11 – Prioritized barriers for CS4 (landfill leachate management)

Category	Barrier
Technical	Lack of suitable technological solutions (closure of the cycle and analytical difficulties for control)
Social	Lack of proper communication to the public regarding PFAS and to plant operators about the state-of-the-art on treatment systems
	Lack of societal awareness of the level of PFAS in various products
Financial	Installation and maintenance costs
Public Health	Lack of risk analysis methodologies
Public Health / Governance	Lack of regulations, compliance limits / limit values
Governance	Slow bureaucratic system for releasing landfill permits, answering clarification requests, etc.
Public Health / Environmental / Technical	Lack of suitable monitoring programs for PFAS

3.4.4 Solution brainstorming & priority actions

The fundamentals of solution strategies are the solutions themselves. In the case of zero pollution strategies, solutions of course include the scientific and technical solutions being developed by the case studies to address PM(T)s (see Section 2.3, Boxes 2, 3 and 4). These technologies address challenges in removing PM(T)s and can also be further developed to address other existing challenges, such as the generation of by-products. However, solutions or actions are needed that address barriers pertaining to the entire CE route and value chain. The solutions should also be actionable and precise, where possible. The varied experiences of the involved stakeholders provide valuable feedback on possible solutions and can best be captured through an open brainstorming process.

One method that worked well for brainstorming solutions was providing every stakeholder with sticky notes to write solutions on, which were then added to specific flipcharts for each prioritized barrier (see Figure Annex-B3). The participants were given approximately 15 minutes to brainstorm on their own with no moderation and could freely stand up to place their sticky notes on the charts. Afterwards, the moderator grouped sticky notes with similar solutions to prepare for the prioritization step (see Figure Annex-B4).

Solutions can be prioritized using several methods, such as coloured stickers (as done for the barriers), thumbs up/down voting, plenary discussions, etc. In the PROMISCES co-creation processes, voting either via thumbs up/down or hand-raising worked well when guided by the moderator. The objective is to gather stakeholder feedback on solutions that should be carried out first or those that should be more heavily emphasized as part of the strategy. By identifying “priority actions” stakeholders are making progress towards the final strategy (see Boxes 11, 12 and 13).

Box 12 – Priority actions to achieve semi-closed drinking water cycle (CS2)

1. Strengthen use restrictions
2. Improve regulation by demanding producer proof of chemical behaviour
3. Raise public awareness
4. Extended responsibilities by producers
5. Standardize (monitoring) methods
6. Implement more strict monitoring of production sites
7. Facilitate synergies in technologies

Box 13 – Priority actions to improve landfill leachate management (CS4)

1. Limit the use of PFAS in industry and encourage research for the production of new, less impactful molecules. Economic leverage (taxation for impactful products and concessions for sustainable ones). Product certification and labeling system.
2. Quickly define the limits for PFAS in discharge into surface waters and sewers.
3. Define clear monitoring program and methodology (analytical methods, identification of indicator parameters for specific matrix) for managing leachate.
4. Develop guidelines and training courses for public administration to reduce the bureaucratic delays of landfill permit authorizations and interpreting new rules/regulations. Suggestion to create these guidelines in tabular form to ease understanding.
5. Define guidelines for risk analyses for emerging contaminants at the European level. Knowledge and best practices from researchers should be collected and shared to support this.
6. Provide public funding for monitoring programs and finding solutions.
7. Expand the extended producer responsibility (EPR) system to cover PFAS to reduce costs and cover not only the costs of treatment, but also those of monitoring and research.
8. Implement labeling system for products containing PFAS and promote actions on green public procurement.
9. Create public opinion information programs (at different age levels including school age).
10. Promote awareness among plant managers about existing technical solutions.
11. Raise awareness in the National System for Environmental Protection (SNPA) for the need to issue guidelines and best practices.

Box 14 – Priority actions to achieve agricultural reuse (CS3)

1. Prioritize financing for water cycle management in budgets (e.g., for developing Reclaimed Water Master Plans by basin, hiring specialized technicians)
2. Implement variable price for water based on consumption and/or incentives for reducing consumption
3. Allow for agile updates to the PM(T)-list
4. Include substances explicitly in legislation
5. Create groups/round tables for each case study / shared responsibility
6. Create protocol to estimate risks to human health / methodology for risk assessment
7. Conduct research on toxicity, presence, risks, etc.
8. Control industrial discharges at the source
9. Establish and communicate treatment performance indicators (e.g. energy/m³)
10. Conduct more research and development for by-product recovery and redox processes
11. Create targeted and adapted communication for each type of user
12. Hire communication professionals in each of the operators and water management administrations for communication with users of reused water

3.4.5 Towards a strategy development

With a list of priority actions, the next logical questions to answer are which actions should be implemented first, who is responsible for their implementation, and how can they be implemented. This is where the stakeholders move towards creating a solution strategy. Within PROMISCES, given the time constraints, this part of the co-creation process focused on answering the following questions:

1. How feasible is the solution?

2. What can I (from the perspective of the stakeholder) or my organization do to help implement this solution?
3. Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?
4. Is this solution somehow already being supported? If so, how or through what mechanism?

To answer the question on feasibility, we asked stakeholders to use coloured sticky notes (green = high feasibility, yellow = medium feasibility, red = low feasibility) to designate each solution. On the sticky note, participants can explain why they view the solution as being easy/hard to implement. This activity could also be combined with the second question if time is restricted. Using the sticky note, participants could define what actions they themselves are able to carry out that would support the solution and mark these as being easily or not so easily feasible.

Stakeholders can make use of the barrier and enabler flipcharts during this activity to identify if any enablers could support a specific solution. For example, in the case of the Besòs River Region, stakeholders identified that EU project funding could support future research needs on by-products and redox processes. For the specific solution strategies, see D5.4.

How the outcomes from this activity can be used to address PM(T)s and PFAS in various circular economy routes is explained in more detail in Chapter 4.

3.4.6 Translating co-creation methods for online processes

As stated in Section 3.3, there may be a need to organize an online co-creation process in order to secure participation from relevant stakeholders. Online tools enable broader participation but present challenges such as reduced sustained attention, easier multitasking, and difficulties for moderators in engaging participants and facilitating inclusive information processing (Matti et al., 2022). However, online co-creation processes are still relevant formats for engaging in participatory processes when stakeholders are more likely to join an online workshop (as also mentioned in section 3.3). The co-creation methods need to be adjusted to fit in an online format.

In PROMISCES, we conducted two online workshops via Zoom, for CS3 (second part) and CS2, using a Miro Board as the interactive platform. Figure B7. Annex-B7 and Figure Annex-B8 illustrate how we translated the in-person methods to identify and prioritize barriers and solutions using a Miro Board.

3.5. Follow-up after co-creation

While feedback should be incorporated within the co-creation itself, after the official “end” of the workshop, follow-up with the stakeholders is needed to ensure all the information is captured correctly. In PROMISCES, we created “output summaries” that transcribed, and, if necessary, translated, the discussions during each part of the co-creation process. As a first step, the case study leaders reviewed the summaries for accuracy, especially regarding translation, and then the summaries were sent to the stakeholders for review.

It is important to note here that it might be necessary to create two versions of the output summary – one for the stakeholders involved and one for the public. The public version should not include any mention of names or organizations of the participating stakeholders due to ethical restriction (see Section 3.2.3). The public versions of all three public summaries are accessible in Annex C, D and E.

Chapters 4 and 5 go into more detail on lessons learnt for future co-creation processes and how to use the co-creation outcomes to work towards achieving the goal of zero pollution.

4. Lessons learnt and reflection

In this chapter, we reflect on the co-creation process applied within PROMISCES, and on the solution strategies developed with the stakeholders. In Section 4.1, we first describe the lessons learnt on the co-creation of solution strategies. In Section 4.2, we reflect on the solution strategies themselves.

4.1. On co-creating solution strategies

4.1.1 Focus of the co-creation process

Several lessons on how to focus the co-creation process were identified. We learnt during the PROMISCES co-creation that it can make more sense to focus the co-creation process on the local case study and sources of emission, rather than individual PM(T) substance-use combinations. Focussing on specific PM(T) substances would make sense if the focus was prevention on a larger scale, such as the EU level, but such a focus is less useful in the local case. The local audience was mainly interested in achieving a local circular economy. This way, the stakeholders can more easily contribute their expertise and the local context can be accounted for better. Such a strategy centred around a local case study is applicable for multiple PM(T) substances and uses at once. Nevertheless, in some cases applying such a local strategy for specific PM(T)s may still be useful. See also PROMISCES Deliverable 5.4, where the results of the co-creation workshops are coupled with the research outputs of PROMISCES.

Additionally, we learnt that selecting the case studies to serve as the focus of co-creation processes should be carried out carefully. Having a local partner involved who knows the local context and sees the added value for themselves or for the case study, helps tremendously with finding the focus of the co-creation process. Added value for a case study could include aspects such as connecting to local stakeholders who are typically hard to reach out to, or sharing the latest research findings with a wider audience. Furthermore, working with a local partner can help with the practical organization of the workshops, especially when it makes more sense to hold the workshop in the local language.

4.1.2 Practical lessons learnt

During the organization of the workshops, it became clear that a balance between the desired planning of the co-creation workshop and the time investment required by the stakeholders (i.e. traveling to/from the workshop and participating in the workshop) was needed. This balance is of course influenced by the level of interest of the stakeholders. For example, stakeholders related to CS3 were very interested, so it was possible to have a full day live workshop, followed by a half day online workshop. For CS4 and CS2, however, interest was lower, and the first workshop was shorter. Therefore, the second and third workshop phases followed immediately after the first phase.

Another lesson was that having the workshops in-person setting was not always possible. For PROMISCES, this was not possible for the CS2 co-creation workshop, which targeted an international group of stakeholders. The stakeholders did not show interest in travelling internationally for a co-creation workshop, so the format was adjusted. Fortunately, the scripts and exercises for the workshop were easily transferred to an online environment, and results could still be gathered. Discussion, however, was more difficult online, especially in a plenary setting, so increasing the number of break-out groups is recommended to establish a lively discussion. These lessons learnt agree with the findings of Wilkerson et al. (2020).

4.1.3 Lessons learnt on steps towards co-creating a solution strategy

During the organization of the workshops, we learnt that a well-defined problem description was essential for a well-focussed workshop (see also section 3.1.1). This helps to develop the workshop structure adequately, anticipate discussions during the workshop, and create a relevant invitation for the stakeholders. A well-defined description made it easier to highlight the added value for stakeholder participation, especially when combined with the local situation focus, instead of a specific PM(T) substance-use combination. For the PROMISCES case studies, a clear problem description was possible, as much was known about the presence and possible solutions for PM(T) substances. However, if less information is available for the problem description, additional steps should be taken for the problem description.

First, an option for getting a clearer picture regarding the problem of PM(T) substances is to use the PM(T) identifier of the PROMISCES decision support framework (DSF). This tool can be used to catalogue a first overview of possible problematic PM(T) substances ([link](#)). Additionally, the PM(T) assessment tool of the DSF ([link](#)) can be used to interpret results from monitoring and identify which of the measured substances are the most problematic. The information from these tools can be used in the problem description as a starting point for the co-creation process.

Second, the solution module of the PROMISCES DSF can be used to select systematic solutions that could be part of a strategy. Within PROMISCES, four systematic solutions also referred to as levels of solutions are identified to address PM(T)s within a circular economy route: prevention, monitoring, risk assessment and treatment. A framework for the selection of possible solutions for PM(T) substances at these four levels is available in the solutions module of the DSF. This framework is outlined in [Deliverable D5.4](#) (Narain-Ford et al., 2025). The DSF will be integrated into the NORMAN Database System as part of its tool collection, ensuring its long-term maintenance and accessibility.

Aside from the steps to explore the problem and possible solutions, it is also possible to give more or specific attention to problem and solution exploration within the solution strategy. In the next section, we will discuss the focus of solution strategies in more detail.

4.2. On the solution strategies

The developed solution strategies can vary largely. For one, the developed solution strategy can vary depending on what is already known about the problem. Within the PROMISCES case studies, there was awareness of the presence of PM(T) substances, and an effort was made to identify the relevant PM(T) substances problems in the case studies. For cases or circular economy routes where PM(T) substances awareness is lacking, more efforts to diagnose and start monitoring within the solution strategy could be needed. Nevertheless, even the PROMISCES case studies still found monitoring to be an important aspect of the strategy, as it is also a way to determine whether the goals of achieving lower PM(T) substances concentrations are achieved.

An additional variation can be caused by the scale of the case for which the solution strategy will be developed. The PROMISCES case studies varied largely in scale, with the scale of CS2 being much larger than CS3. Therefore, CS2 focused more on changes that could impact the system as a whole, such as regulating the introduction of new substances. In contrast, CS3 had solutions that focused on the local case, such as calling for more cross-sectoral collaboration and communication in the catchment and region.

Furthermore, the circular economy route itself and how well-established it is can cause differences in the solution strategy opted for. For CS3, the agricultural use of reclaimed water was very clearly

accepted, so not much effort was put on solutions for that. Instead, a large focus was placed on accepting potable use of reclaimed water. For CS2, the case was on protecting a source of drinking water that is already being used, which caused acceptance to be less relevant.

Lastly, the importance of different types of solutions can vary. Below, we discuss five points and how they could vary in co-created solution strategies:

- **Knowledge base.** Presentations from the PROMISCES researchers provided information on scientific and technical solutions within the PROMISCES workshops. This gives a clear knowledge base for which scientific and technical solution could work. As a consequence, these solutions were placed alongside other actions to achieve the required boundary conditions. This may not always be so for other cases, as there may be more importance on evaluating scientific and technical solutions in the solution strategies.
- **Prevention.** While prevention was always found to be important, it was not identified as an overarching solution, certainly not when legacy pollution is relevant. This was the case for CS2, where legacy pollution was an important factor.
- **Limit values.** There were differences in the strategies' need for clear targets, guidelines or limit values. This varied within the PROMISCES case studies, as some case studies called for clear guidelines and limit values they should strive for (CS3 and CS4). This was less clear for CS2, as the focus was mostly on PFAS, for which a limit value for drinking water is already established. Nevertheless, all the case studies called for more flexible or agile updating of PM(T) lists or limit values.
- **Financing.** All the case studies mentioned the challenges presented by the high costs of monitoring and treatment and the need to ensure that financial means are available.
- **Public awareness.** Public awareness was considered important for a strategy in all the cases. However, there were differences in how. For CS3, public acceptance of the reused water was named to be important, so public awareness was approached from the perspective of acceptance of a specific circular economy route. For CS2 and CS4, it was found to be important from a behavioural change and preventive perspective.

4.3. Reflection and follow-up

The co-created solution strategies developed within PROMISCES provide a clearly prioritized list of actions to take. Most of the objectives defined for the workshops were achieved (Table 6). However, there are also some limitations, most notably on the actions for the participations. The developed solutions focus on listing the most important actions, with no specifics regarding timing or priority.

As a follow-up for these workshops, a focus can be placed on making these actions more concrete. Additionally, some of the identified priority actions require a political or societal discussion in a follow-up, for example on assigning financial, preventive or curative (treatment) responsibilities. Lastly, the follow-up process may need to have attention for capacity building programs or training for stakeholders to ensure the effective implementation of solutions.

Nevertheless, the solution strategies (output summaries; Annex C, D, E) can be used by the stakeholders who participated in the workshops to integrate the aspects identified during the co-creation process into regional/national documents. For example, the strategy for CS3 can be used to update the water reuse plan of the Besòs River Basin.

Table 6. Conclusion on PROMISCES co-creation objectives.

PROMISCES Co-Creation Objective	Conclusion
Bring together stakeholders from various disciplines to explore challenges regarding PM(T)s, including PFAS	Mostly succeeded. The most important barriers for establishing the circular economy route were identified. The workshops integrated perspectives from diverse disciplines, although it was noted that some important sectors were underrepresented or missing.
Identify potential solutions for these challenges	Succeeded. The priority solutions and actions for establishing the circular economy route were identified.
Evaluate the conditions necessary for their success	Succeeded, by looking multi-disciplinary at the problem, there was also much attention the required boundary conditions
Reflect on what actions the participating stakeholders, both as individuals and institutions, could take to implement the proposed solutions	Partly succeeded. The developed solutions focus on listing the most important actions, with no specifics regarding timing or priority.

5. Conclusion and recommendations

The PROMISCES workshops provide valuable lessons for the organization of co-creation workshops, future projects, and for policy makers at both a European and national level. This deliverable contributes to the zero-pollution ambition by showing how solution strategies can be co-created. Such solution strategies may contribute to a toxic-free environment and the safe reuse of materials. The main conclusions and lessons learnt are:

- The PROMISCES workshops reinforce the importance of including the local context and a well-defined problem statement in organizing a successful co-creation process. Furthermore, it helps to keep the process flexible to account for the local context and the stakeholders' needs. As such, the role of local partners is essential in organizing successful workshops. In future projects, it would help to involve local partners early in the process, to clearly communicate the added benefits of such co-creation workshops to them, and to reserve funding for their involvement.
- Stakeholders from the entire CE route should be invited to participate in co-creation processes, including stakeholders who do not only focus on scientific and technical solutions for PM(T). An involved local partner is crucial for the identification of stakeholders.
- It is recommended that stakeholder interaction continues in the future to develop suggested actions into a comprehensive and collaborative strategy. Political engagement with such future interaction is necessary, especially for actions that involve assigning financial or preventive responsibility.
- Furthermore, the input received from the stakeholders during the workshops give valuable insights for policy makers, both on the European as the national level. The results of the PROMISCES project are translated into recommendations for supporting the evaluation and implementation of relevant EU policy strategies and directives in Deliverable D5.8 (Hartmann et al., 2025; available via <https://zenodo.org/communities/promisces>). D5.8 provides policymakers at the European and national level with policy recommendations to better manage PM(T)s in the soil-water-sediment system, supporting the comprehensive and coordinated management of PM(T) substances across their lifecycle. The aim is to identify and address the inconsistencies, gaps, and uncertainties in existing EU regulations, providing EU policymakers with recommendations and suggested courses of action to safeguard both human health and the environment. The boundary conditions mentioned during the co-creation workshops are included in this report.

The main conclusions and lessons learnt on the solution strategies themselves are:

- Some aspects of the strategy can be expected to always be relevant, such as as monitoring to keep track of emission sources, establishing clear regulatory threshold values for compounds, accounting for new substances with rapid legislation change and, ensuring the availability of financial means for the costly monitoring and treatment. Furthermore, it is expected that a solution strategy should always call for multiple types of solutions.
- The importance of the different aspects within a strategy can vary. For example, while prevention should always be considered, it is not an overarching solution when addressing legacy pollution (i.e., pollution that is already in the environment). Similarly, the importance of curative solutions may vary depending on the situation.

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Annex A: Preliminary Survey Questions for Wastewater Reuse for Irrigation Workshop

Introduction

Thank you for participating in this survey. The survey has been sent to all participants invited for a stakeholder workshop organized by the European research project [PROMISCES](#). In this workshop, we will discuss 1) to what extent growing concerns about how the health and environmental risks posed by a specific group of chemical substances may affect the plan for using reclaimed water coming from Wastewater Treatment Plants (WWTPs) for the irrigation of crops in the Besòs Tordera region and 2) how these concerns can be addressed. The workshop will greatly benefit from your participation in this preliminary survey, even if you are not familiar with these water reuse plans or with the concerns associated with chemical pollution and respective solutions. Filling in this survey will provide us with an initial overview of stakeholder knowledge and opinions and will take about 10 minutes.

Why should you participate?

- **Contribute** to a more effective discussion with local stakeholders
- **Share** your opinion and needs regarding the use of reclaimed water for irrigation
- **Provide** additional information you feel is important to be considered

Part 1: Stakeholder Identification

1. Please enter your first name

[open answer]

2. Please enter your last name

[open answer]

3. What is the name of the organization or institution that you work for?

[open answer]

Part 2 – Reclaimed Water

4. How familiar are you with the Reclaimed Water Master Plan (RWMP) for the Besòs Tordera region?

Not at all	A little	Basic idea	Pretty familiar	Closely involved
○	○	○	○	○

5. *What is your opinion of the plan to build Reclaimed Water Plants?*

<i>Very unfavourable</i>	<i>Unfavourable</i>	<i>Neutral</i>	<i>Favourable</i>	<i>Very favourable</i>	<i>Don't know</i>
○	○	○	○	○	○

6. *What do you see as the primary goal of the Reclaimed Water Plants? And what is your primary concern?*

[open answer]

In the workshop we will focus on using reclaimed water for irrigation of crops. For accomplishing this goal, general conditions have to be met. The reclaimed water must be sufficiently **clean and safe to use**, and **costs for this treatment** should not be too high. Because of increasing demands for other purposes (irrigation of parks, street cleaning, industry, underground water stocks (aquifers)), **allocation** questions can arise (i.e. which purpose should get how much water), as well as concerns about the **impact on the Besos river ecology** when less water from waste water treatment plants is flowing into the river.

7. *In your view, how important do you think these aspects are for using reclaimed water for irrigation of crops?*

	Not important at all	Not important	Neutral	Important	Very important	Don't know
Safety	<input type="radio"/>					
Costs	<input type="radio"/>					
Allocation	<input type="radio"/>					
Impacts on river ecology	<input type="radio"/>					
[other]	<input type="radio"/>					

8. *Are there other aspects important, not mentioned here?*

[open answer]

9. *How do the above-mentioned aspects relate to the primary goal of the Reclaimed Water Plants stated earlier in Question #6? And how do they relate to your primary concern?*

[open answer]

Part 3: Micropollutants (PM(T) substances)

10. *How much do you know about pollution of water resources by PM(T) substances?*

Nothing	A little	Basic idea	Pretty familiar	A lot
<input type="radio"/>				

11. How concerned are you about pollution of water resources by PM(T)-substances? And what about PM(T)-substances in reclaimed water for irrigation of crops?

	Not concerned at all	A little concerned	Neutral	Concerned	Very concerned	Don't know
PM(T) pollution in water resources	○	○	○	○	○	○
PM(T) substances in reclaimed water for irrigation of crops	○	○	○	○	○	○

12. How do PM(T)-substances affect your primary goal of the Reclaimed Water Plants? And how do they affect your primary concern?

[open answer]

13. What kind of substances (groups, sources, etc) are you concerned about in reclaimed water for irrigation of crops? Multiple answers possible

PFAS substances

Industrial compounds

Medicines and drugs

Other pharmaceutical compounds

Veterinary medicines

Pesticides

other, namely:...

none

14. To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the removal of PM(T)-substances from reclaimed water for irrigation of crops?

PM(T)-substances should be removed, when...

	Totally disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Totally agree	Don't know
there are concerns, but no risk has been established	○	○	○	○	○	○
an environmental risk has been established	○	○	○	○	○	○
a human risk has been established	○	○	○	○	○	○

a guidance on how to deal with the substance has been established	<input type="radio"/>					
there is regulation	<input type="radio"/>					

15. *Please explain your response to the previous question.*

[open answer]

Part 4: Options for addressing PM(T) substances

There are several ways to deal with PM(T) substances in RWPs. It is possible to limit the use of PM(T) substances in industry by **substitution** of PM(T) substances by less harmful compounds. Alternatively, the emissions of PM(T) substances (to waste water) can be **prevented**, for example by having better waste management or stricter rules regarding discharge. Further, it is possible to remove PM(T) substances from the wastewater by having additional **treatment** of the wastewater in the wastewater treatment plant or the reclaimed water plants. Lastly, it is possible to keep close tabs on the risks posed by PM(T) substances by **monitoring** the presence and concentrations of the PM(T) substances in the wastewater or reclaimed water.

It is possible that a strategy to deal with PM(T) substances in RWPs consists of a combination of these options.

16. *How would you rate the importance and feasibility of the described options for addressing PM(T) substances in the RWPs? And are there other options not mentioned here?*

		Very low	Low	Neutral	High	Very high	Don't know
Substitution	Importance	<input type="radio"/>					
	feasibility	<input type="radio"/>					
Prevention	Importance	<input type="radio"/>					
	feasibility	<input type="radio"/>					
Treatment	Importance	<input type="radio"/>					
	feasibility	<input type="radio"/>					
Monitoring	Importance	<input type="radio"/>					
	feasibility	<input type="radio"/>					

17. *Please explain your answers provided to the previous question*

[open answer]

18. *Are there other options for addressing PM(T) substances that you'd like to suggest, in addition to the four options listed above? And how would you rank these other options in terms of importance and feasibility?*

[open answer]

Context

19. *Which aspects may influence the need for removing PM(T) substances (costs, energy costs, urgency, droughts, etc.)? Is this influence negative or positive? (multiple answers are possible) Please explain.*

[open answer]

20. *Do you have any other information or thoughts that you would like to share at this time?*

[open answer]

Annex B: Impression photos of the PROMISCES in-person and online co-creation workshops

Figure B1. Case study leader presents the barriers and enablers identified in her world café group at the CS3 workshop.

Figure B2. Participants at the CS4 co-creation workshop use red, yellow and green stickers to prioritize identified barriers for management of PFAS-containing leachate.

Figure B3. Participants place sticky notes with ideas for solutions to address the prioritized barriers on flipcharts that list each barrier (CS3 workshop).

Figure B4. Co-creation workshop moderator grouped sticky notes that offered similar ideas for solutions by attaching them to one another (CS3 workshop).

Figure B5. At the CS4 co-creation workshop, participants used coloured sticky notes to indicate whether the actions they could take to support solution #4 would be easy or more difficult to carry out.

Figure B6. Demonstrative flipchart of public health barriers identified during the CS3 workshop (language is in Catalan). Prioritized barriers have been encircled in red.

Figure B7. Miro Board screenshot of the barrier and enabler identification for the CS2 co-creation workshop.

Figure B8. Miro Board screenshot of the solution identification and voting during the CS2 co-creation workshop.

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Topic: **LC-GD-8-1-2020** - Innovative, systemic zero-pollution solutions to protect health, environment, and natural resources from persistent and mobile chemicals

Preventing Recalcitrant Organic Mobile Industrial chemicals for Circular Economy in the soil-sediment-water System

D5.6 Annex C

Summary of Co-creation Stakeholder Workshops for the Danube Basin (CS2)

**Developing a system-wide, zero pollution strategy to ensure future drinking water production along
the Danube**

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The result of this activity is presented in the table below. Table 4. The results from the fourth part of the workshop. For each solution, the stakeholders judged the feasibility using the colour of the sticky note and indicated actions for their organisation.	65

1. Background

1.2 Current situation

The Danube River is a fundamental source of water abstraction for drinking water production. This production process relies on riverbank filtration (RBF) systems. RBF systems naturally filter river water through the surrounding sediments as it flows from the river to nearby wells, effectively reducing some contaminants' concentrations before it is extracted for drinking water treatment. However, the chemical water quality is increasingly impacted by various discharges into the river, with wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) being the largest contributors. These discharges contain a range of persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT) substances. Some of these PMT substances, such as PFAS, are hardly removed in the RBF systems. This raises concerns about the future reliability of RBFs for drinking water production, and introduces the need for additional advanced treatment processes. Finally, pressure on the drinking water quality and production process will increase as the recast of Directive 2020/2184 "on the quality of water intended for human consumption" is implemented.

To address this issue, it is necessary to consider solutions that go beyond treatment of such PMT substances during drinking water production. This broader approach requires focusing on upstream solutions, such as reducing emission at WWTPs, identifying and controlling industrial discharges, and reconsidering the use of certain chemicals. This last approach includes examining whether specific chemicals are essential for use and if their potential substitutes are safer alternatives with desirable environmental behaviour.

Regulatory updates play a critical role in addressing water quality issues. There is a concern that ensuring future drinking water production through RBFs may not be guaranteed without costly additional treatment, particularly if drinking water standards become more stringent. The EU Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive is updated. The co-legislators aligned the thresholds and timelines for tertiary treatment (i.e. the removal of nitrogen and phosphorus) and quaternary treatment (that is, the removal of a broad spectrum of micropollutants). By 2039 and 2045 respectively, Member states will have to ensure the application of tertiary and quaternary treatment in larger plants of 150 000 population equivalent (p.e.) and above, with intermediate targets in 2033 and 2036 for tertiary treatment and in 2033 and 2039 for quaternary treatment ([Urban wastewater: Council and Parliament reach a deal on new rules for more efficient treatment and monitoring - Consilium \(europa.eu\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32020R2184)).

Finally, an additional challenge to consider is legacy contamination within the river system. This type of contamination refers to the long-lasting environmental presence of chemicals, such as PFAS, often from historical industrial or consumer use. Therefore, even if emission from WWTPs and/or industries along the river are significantly reduced or eliminated, the long-term impact of existing PMT pollution would persist. Because the full extent of this legacy contamination contribution to overall PMT concentrations in the Danube River is still uncertain, it must be considered when developing future water quality management strategies.

1.3 PROMISCES Case study

Within the PROMISCES case study, PFAS within the Danube River and RBF systems are studied. Specifically, the case study focuses on developing methods:

- for the identification and quantification of the origin of selected chemicals discharged to the Danube River.

- to assess the behaviour of these chemicals during filtration in the riverbanks and during drinking water abstraction.
- to identify effective measures to control pollution levels in rivers and in drinking water impacted by rivers.

2. Co-Creation Process to Create Zero-Pollution Strategies

To create a viable strategy for dealing with micropollutants and ensuring future drinking water production along the Danube, a system view is essential, both in understanding the problem(s) and identifying potential solutions. To support this, PROMISCES organized a co-creation process with stakeholders. This interactive online co-creation workshop took place on October 2 2024, and it involved 11 stakeholders. The goals of this in-person workshop were to (Figure 1):

- Define the problem of micropollutants in the Danube and the future drinking water production
- Identify barriers and other factors that need to be addressed to ensure future drinking water
- Define solutions to overcome these barriers
- Co-create an interdisciplinary, system-wide strategy that incorporates the defined solutions and needed actors

To prepare the stakeholders for the ensuing discussion on barriers and solutions, PROMISCES created a preliminary online survey. In this survey, participants could provide their opinion on the importance and feasibility of various solution types. Additionally, the workshop made use of the online “Miro” to involve the participants in the group and gather their direct input. In the Miro board, the participants can work together on a digital whiteboard. The Miro board was set up to facilitate discussion and collaboration for each of the parts in the workshop.

Figure 1. Structure and agenda of the online workshop.

3. Co-Creation Workshop

3.1 Part 0: Introduction

The workshop began with an explanation of the co-creation process. Additionally, the context and problem surrounding micropollutants within the Danube were explained together with an explanation of the case study activities.

Figure 2 The online workshop. Above: stakeholders collaboration on the Miro board. Below: the Zoom meeting (note: only the presenters are shown, to ensure the privacy of the participants.)

3.2 Workshop Part 1: Problem Definition

In the first part of the workshop, the focus was on defining and discussing the problem, to get all the stakeholders on the same page. This was done by:

- Firstly, presenting a brief overview of the problem by a member of the PROMISCES case study team.

- Secondly, the initial survey was used to give a first overview of the opinion of various solution types by the stakeholders.
- Finally, there was an opportunity for the stakeholders to provide their reflection and to discuss the problem definition.

The discussion of the problem definition did not lead to large changes from the initial description of the problem, but did lead to a shared view of the problem among the stakeholders.

3.3 Workshop Part 2: Barriers & Enablers

3.3.1 Identifying Barriers

During the second part of the co-creation workshop, barriers and enablers were identified in a world café setting in six relevant aspects. This was done in break out groups, and the barriers and enablers were noted down in an online collaboration space (the Miro board).

The output from this session is presented in Table 1, with barriers and enablers listed per category. The barriers indicated in bold were prioritised in the next workshop phase (see below).

Table 1. Barriers and enablers for the problem of microcontaminants in the Danube. The bolded text are the prioritized barriers.

BARRIERS	Enablers
Environmental health	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Substance properties result in wide dispersion • Groundwater: PFAS sources, movements • Transformation processes unknown / unclear in speed • Legacy pollution (Diverse presence in nature - long lasting supply from the environments) • PFAS contamination in many regions unknown • Very slow degradation rate in most matrices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some industries have high emissions, which makes them suitable for a pre-treatment • Where does pollution come from? how much comes from groundwater? (PFAS pollution) • organisms able to degrade PFAS as a co-substrate • use of soil to address less complicated compounds
Public health	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is the health effect and dose of each PMT substance known? Both academic and 'broader' • Unclear which substance is responsible for health effect • What risk is acceptable? esp. for drinking water. Emotions are concerned and hinder open discussion • Lack of regulation or awareness (and effect) on doses of medication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General information on PFAS / public awareness • responsible way of communication, vs misuse of information • 'effect analytics', such as bio essays • more precise treatment (for example near hospitals)
Social	

BARRIERS	Enablers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People are not aware of PMTs (except a little bit about PFAS) • limited education of general public (without alarming) • Certain knowledge of chemistry needed to understand what PFAS or even PMT are • increasing need for pharmaceutical compounds • social solid waste management is sometimes lacking • tricky advertisement of "flushable" products • Expectation of the public, that things needs to be known without uncertainties before action is taken • High societal request for products that contain PMT substances 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anything that makes people aware of PMTs: ads, packaging that says "PFAS-free", news articles, "horror" stories • Documentaries, Deepper news articles - Example - Forever_MAP - • distinguish between essential and non-essential use of chemicals • Nature connection/recreational uses increases awareness on waste/pollution (ecosystem services awareness) • Better education in chemistry • High-profile court cases (e.g. Dutch government vs. 3M) • Togetherness to address the issue
Technical	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information barrier: which PFAS to measure? Which are important? Which methods? What are their price? What is the removal rate? • Legacy pollution (Diverse presence in nature - long lasting supply from the environments) • Research results are usually very uncertain • Groundwater: how do you sample PFAS • Treatment techniques can be detrimental to the environment (energy intensive) - priority / balance of what is more important? • Difficult substance properties for removal & destruction • Regulation may come in the future, which can affect treatment options/choices now • GAC: What to do with the waste? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deep ocean sinks? • Method to measure sum parameter • Monitoring / mapping of contamination • Quaternary treatment at WWTPs (e.g. ozone) • Research about removal technologies and their efficiency • Innovation in treatment / destruction
Financial	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs of treatment methods (financial and energy); not all countries are able to afford tertiary/quaternary treatment. • Penalties for larger companies will have to be paid by consumers (eg medicine cost increase) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase treatment cost (drinking water or WWTP) • "Penalties" for producers - e.g. health insurance doesn't cover PFAS illnesses • Governmental support (e.g. financial)

BARRIERS	Enablers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High costs for analysis • Yearly cost of treatment of annual PFAS production is higher than the global GDP • Costs of PFAS destruction (only at extremely high temperatures) • Banning pesticides could increase food price 	
Legislative, Governance	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of regulation and enforcing existing fire extinguishing systems • Polluters have the responsibility to report pollution, which does not always work in practice • Some laws work better on paper than in reality • Balancing with economic interest for production and use • Legislation is always lacking behind on advances of research and/or the creation of new chemicals • Focus on single chemicals, in relation to the high number of new chemicals • (lack of) threshold values 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better database on actual emissions - legislative force to make it happen • better regulation of registration/permissions of chemicals • New academic insights could help formulate new legislation, (e.g. sum parameters, or health effect parameters) • Development in analytics, so substances can be detected in low levels

3.3.2 Prioritizing Barriers

After finalizing the lists of barriers, the participants voted on the priority of the barriers in the Miro board. The most important barriers (those with the highest number of votes) are indicated in bold in Table 1 above and are listed below.

Most prioritized barriers had a link to the categories of technical (4), legislative/governance (2), and environmental (2). Additionally, one priority barrier was identified within the financial category and one in the social category. Note that the barriers can be related to multiple categories (Table 2).

Table 2. The complete list of prioritized barriers.

	Prioritized barrier	Category
1	Difficult substance properties for removal & destruction	Technical
2	Legislation is always lacking behind on advances of research and/or the creation of new chemicals	Legislative
3	High societal request of products that contain PMT substances	Social
4	Legacy pollution (Diverse presence in nature - long lasting supply from the environments)	Environmental and technical

	Prioritized barrier	Category
5	Information barrier: which PFAS to measure? Which are important? Which methods? What is their price? What is the removal rate?	Technical
6	Treatment techniques can be detrimental to the environment (energy intensive) - priority / balance of what is more important?	Environmental and technical
7	Costs of treatment methods (financial and energy); not all countries are able to afford tertiary/quaternary treatment.	Financial
8	Balancing regulation between protection and economic interest for production and use	Legislative

3.4 Workshop Part 3: Identifying Solutions

3.4.1 Brainstorming Solutions

The last step was to identify solutions for the eight prioritized barriers. This started with a 'brain-dump' by the participants, in which they provided as many solutions as possible for each of the identified barriers, in the Miro board.

The results of this brainstorm of solutions are indicated in Table 3, together with the clusters they belong to (see below).

Table 3. Solutions proposed by the participants for the eight prioritized barriers.

Difficult substance properties for removal & destruction
<p>Green Chemistry Research & Biological degradation facilitation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Find a way to add some chemical group to these substances to make them more easily accessible to biological degradation • stronger support of development of "green" chemistry • research on biological degradation and how to increase the rates <p>Strengthening use restrictions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • very strong restriction of use • restriction on use • implement strict advanced producer responsibility <p>Research Investments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • enhance investments in research • advances in technology needed (in cases avoidance does not work)
Legislation is always lacking behind on advances of research and/or the creation of new chemicals
<p>Regulation by demanding producer proof of chemical behaviour</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU-wide enforcing of research into persistence & toxicity of new substances BEFORE they are produced, not after (Global would be even better but unfeasible) • Strict application of the precautionary principle, so only allow industrial use for substances thoroughly investigated for their environmental fate • implement strict advanced producer responsibility

- Stronger pressure on chemical production by legislations (e.g. very strong proof to be provided for new chemicals with regard to their effects on human and ecosystem health)
- stronger requirements for licences for chemicals

Communication with General Public to raise awareness and reduce demand

- Communication campaigns - raising awareness of the potential problems of new chemicals - Reduction of demand

Improve application of knowledge in legislation

- Better communication / exchange of knowledge

High societal request of products that contain PMT substances

Price adjustments on products

- Price of products should be "real" - i.e. should include costs of remediation

Raising public awareness

- Raise awareness of ecosystems services and the harm from chemicals
- Communication campaigns - raising awareness of the potential problems of new chemicals
- Awareness raising for wellbeing without the need for consumption
- Behaviour changes

Legacy pollution (Diverse presence in nature - long lasting supply from the environments)

More strict monitoring of production sites

- Start monitoring activities in places based on catchment scale models / historical information
- increase legal responsibility of producers of pollution (at least for the future)

Active approach to legacy pollution

- identification of locations, development of remediation technologies and their application
- More research to identify legacy pollution sites
- Containment of known legacy pollution sites until appropriate treatment becomes available

Information barrier: which PFAS to measure? Which are important? Which methods? What is their price? What is the removal rate?

Standardize (monitoring) methods

- Development of "standard methods" of sampling and analyzing PFAS
- Guidelines can do heavy lifting (e.g. focus on the sum of 24 PFAS)

Innovate in methods

- Innovative analytical methods (such as non-targeted, biosensors)

Treatment techniques can be detrimental to the environment (energy intensive) - priority / balance of what is more important?

Priorities on how to approach

- Apply life cycle assessment with appropriate indicators to decide where to treat and where not to treat

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open discussion needed on priorities • Focus treatment where it is needed most (e.g. wastewater directly at its source) <p>Facilitate synergies in technologies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connect technologies - waste incineration produces the heat required to demolish the substances • Avoidance first, treatment second
<p>Costs of treatment methods (financial and energy); not all countries are able to afford tertiary/quaternary treatment.</p>
<p>Alternative water sources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consideration of alternative sources (mainly for new plants) - Deep groundwater instead of bank filtration etc. <p>Extended responsibilities by producers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emitters / producers should help pay for remediation • Avoid pollution: Do not allow export of chemicals restricted in EU from production in the EU into other parts of the world.
<p>Balancing regulation between protection and economic interest for production and use</p>
<p>Raising general population awareness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public awareness could increase public (and thus political) pressure to increase protection - i.e. health effects of unborn babies <p>Political Focus / lobbying</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong lobbying for public interest (environment/water) on high legislative level (EU). Limitation/Restriction of lobbying from chemical industry. • Restrict and control lobbying of industry. • Advanced producer responsibility

3.4.2 Selecting Priority Actions

After the 'brain-dump' activity, the identified solutions were clustered into separate actions. During this clustering, the participants discussed the proposed actions. The clusters are presented in the above table as the bold headings for the individual suggestions. There was a large discussion, especially on the extended user responsibility, and it was noted that producers themselves were not present in the workshop.

Next, the clusters were prioritized by voting on the Miro board. Based on the voting, the following seven priority focus areas for actions were identified:

1. Strengthening use restrictions
2. Regulation by demanding producer proof of chemical behaviour
3. Raising public awareness
4. Extended responsibilities by producers
5. Standardize (monitoring) methods
6. More strict monitoring of production sites

7. Facilitate synergies in technologies

3.5 Workshop Part 4: Towards a strategy

In the fourth part of the workshop, there were three activities:

1. Stakeholders judged the feasibility of the solution clusters using the colour of the sticky notes in the Miro board (green = more feasible; yellow = less feasible).
2. Stakeholders identified actions for themselves for each of the solutions;
3. Stakeholder identified who else is needed/has responsibility for each of the actions

The result of this activity is presented in the table below. Table 44. The results from the fourth part of the workshop. For each solution, the stakeholders judged the feasibility using the colour of the sticky note and indicated actions for their organisation.

Solution cluster 1: Strengthening use restrictions
4 green sticky notes Comments: - probably more effective and implementable than relying on public awareness and consumer responsibility
3 yellow sticky notes Comments: - political will (EU level and beyond) is needed
0 red sticky notes
What can I (or my organization) do to help implement this solution?
TU Wien: - show substance persistence & mobility - contribution to national and international organizations - contribute to the co-creation workshops BME: - Publish research results
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?
EU/WHO
Solution cluster 2: Regulation by demanding producer proof of chemical behaviour
3 green sticky notes
3 yellow sticky notes Comments:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficult to push it through legislative mechanisms - political will (EU level and beyond is needed)
0 red sticky notes
What can I (or my organization) do to help implement this solution?
TU Wien: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify which information on chemicals is needed Tyrol: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Opinion/comment on the implementation of the WW directive
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?
Solution cluster 3: Raising public awareness
1 green sticky note
3 yellow sticky notes
Comments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - political will (EU level and beyond) is needed
4 red sticky notes
Comments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • public awareness should be used to help strengthen regulation. relying on public awareness for consumer behaviour change will not work on a long term basis • Requires better education, which is not easy/fast to achieve • you only reach a relatively small bubble. Other interests are stronger promoted • Difficult to breach peoples thresholds for information
What can I (or my organization) do to help implement this solution?
TU Wien: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public presentations - Education, raising the awareness of young people WTP Linz (LINZ AG): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mentioning the issues in guided tours BME: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Education, raising the awareness of young people Tyrol: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public relations
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NGOs focusing on these type of problems - Schools

Solution cluster 4: Extended responsibilities by producers
2 green sticky notes Comments: - already on its way
3 yellow sticky notes Comments: - But not limited to one branch as currently proposed. And then identification of responsible producers might become challenging.
0 red sticky notes
What can I (or my organization) do to help implement this solution?
TU Wien: - Contribute to (EU) working groups on legislative changes
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?
- Organisations representing groups of producers
Solution cluster 5: Standardize (monitoring) methods
4 green sticky notes Comments: - this is in what science has a long history of establishing
2 yellow sticky notes
0 red sticky notes
What can I (or my organization) do to help implement this solution?
TU Wien: - Take part in projects focusing on method standardization
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?
- Standardisation organisations (ISO...)
Solution cluster 6: More strict monitoring of production and polluted sites

4 green sticky notes
3 yellow sticky notes
0 red sticky notes
What can I (or my organization) do to help implement this solution?
<p>WTP Linz (LINZ AG):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - restriction of allowed pollutions and forced analysis <p>TU Wien:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Propose monitoring in projects - Extend the scope of monitoring by modeling to improve basis for management <p>Tyrol:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - implementation of the ww directive, "water supervision"
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local authorities
Solution cluster 7: Facilitate synergies in technologies
1 green sticky note
Comments:
3 yellow sticky notes
<p>Comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is also a legislative question. Should be incorporated in the BAT process for industries - Might be challenging in timing and in spacial distribution
0 red sticky notes
What can I (or my organization) do to help implement this solution?
<i>None indicated</i>
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?
BAT producing groups

4. Reflections and Conclusion

The structure of the workshop resulted in an action list of how to deal with PM(T) substances in the Danube basin. The workshop made clear that an action plan is needed, and priority actions for this were identified.

Two of the priority actions call for clear and strong regulation from legislation. These regulations focus on the prevention of the use of harmful components (such as PFAS) by strengthening use restrictions and regulating new chemicals by demanding producer proof of chemical behaviour. Additional focus on prevention was suggested by raising public awareness to reduce the demand for products with harmful components.

Further, the stakeholders focus on improving monitoring of PMT substances, by increasing the monitoring of production and polluted sites, and by standardizing monitoring methods. For the technologies.

The stakeholders suggested that the costs of the additional treatment and monitoring could be covered via extended producer responsibility. It should be noted that producers were not present in the workshop, and there was quite some discussion on whether this would actually be acceptable for the producers. It was noted that a strong political will is needed. Another selected priority solution was to focus on facilitating synergies in technologies, although none of the participants indicated that they could contribute to this action, and there were doubts on the feasibility for this solution.

The proposed priority actions highlight legislative, social and financial boundary conditions that must be met to address problems along the circular economy route. Special importance was given to clear and strong regulation.

Due to the time constraint of the stakeholder workshop, the various actions from the involved stakeholders are merely listed in the following table, without specifics regarding timing or priority. It is therefore recommended that stakeholder interaction continues in the future to transition these suggested actions into a comprehensive and collaborative strategy.

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Preventing Recalcitrant Organic Mobile Industrial chemicals for Circular Economy in the soil-sediment-water System

D5.6 Annex D

Summary of two Co-creation Stakeholder Workshops for the Besòs River Basin (CS3)

Developing a system-wide, zero pollution strategy for the reuse of water for agricultural use

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1. Introduction

Over the course of two co-creation workshops, local and regional representatives of water utility organisations, municipalities, engineering companies, research institutes and the agricultural sector met in Granollers, Spain to discuss options and limitations of agricultural reuse in the Besòs River area. Reusing wastewater is needed to cope with the effects of climate change in Mediterranean countries and is an important route towards a circular economy more broadly. However, whether water treatment solutions deliver safe and cost-effective reclaimed water is dependent on many factors. Therefore, the EU research project PROMISCES organized both these [stakeholder co-creation workshops](#). The following document describes the process, initial outcomes as well as the results obtained from the 1st and 2nd workshop meetings.

2. Background

2.1 Current situation

The Catalan Water Agency (ACA: Agència Catalana de l'Aigua) seeks to promote water reuse in the Besòs River Basin to mitigate water restrictions and consumption cuts which are occurring due to recent periods of severe droughts. To this end, 64 municipalities working together in the Consorci Besòs Tordera (CBT) initiated the Reclaimed Water Master Plan (RWMP). This plan involves the construction of a number of Reclaimed Water Plants (RWPs) and transportation infrastructure to meet urban, agricultural, industrial and environmental water demands.

In 2022, about 95% of the water in the river basin came from wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) discharges. Part of those discharges could be used for agricultural irrigation to alleviate the consumption of drinking water. For the purpose of agricultural reuse, emerging contaminants, such as specific chemical substances or medicine residues coming from both industrial and household sources, would need to be removed. Specifically, over the past decades, concerns have been growing about chemicals which do not degrade (persistent substances; P), can easily spread throughout the environment (mobile substances; M) and are suspected to harm organisms (toxic substances: T). In the current design of the RWPs, removing PMT substances is not considered. However, this might be needed if the water is to be used for agricultural purposes (irrigation) to prevent that the PMT concentrations found in crops exceed human and environmental safety levels. Moreover, expected future regulations may demand that (some of the) PMT substances be removed from reclaimed water for agricultural and other uses.

2.2 Addressing PMT risks for agricultural use in the Reclaimed Water Master Plan

As part of the PROMISCES EU research project, Consorci Besòs Tordera (CBT) and other partners like Eurecat and IDAEA-CSIC are collaborating at the Wastewater Treatment Plant from Montornès del Vallès in testing water treatment technologies. This case study in the Urban River Lab is investigating whether these technologies provide cost-effective solutions for removing micro-contaminants so that the treated water can be applied safely for agricultural irrigation. Cost-effective solutions are sought via hybrid combinations of technologies.

In January and December 2022, about 20 chemical compounds were identified as micropollutants in the wastewater stream entering Montornès del Vallès. While the source of these chemicals is difficult

to identify, the wastewater stream can be characterized as 60% industrial, 40% municipal. In the case study, the wastewater is treated by an Electrochemical Advanced Oxidation Process (EAOP) combined with a wetland, and this treated water is applied for crops irrigation (lettuce). To determine what levels of pollutant concentration can be left in water for agricultural use, risk assessment for direct (crop) and indirect (fodder for cattle) consumption will be conducted. Based on the results, recommendations for farmers will be constructed for crop selection and agricultural best practices that minimize the transfer of micro-contaminants into the edible parts of crops.

2.3 Prospects and impacts

The results of the case study will be interesting for the entire Besòs River region, since multiple reclamation water plants (RWP) are foreseen. The design of these RWPs is based on conventional treatment technologies, which do not take chemical compounds as micropollutants into consideration. More broadly, experience with treatment technologies might be addressed by members of the Catalan Water Partnership (CWP). The construction of the first RWP will start in 2024.

Since water shortages can be severe, treated wastewater may also be used by industry, municipalities (e.g. street cleaning), owners of golf courses or even drinking water plants (DWP). Currently, there is only one drinking water plant downstream of the Urban River Lab (Besòs DWP), which treats groundwater mixed with treated water from the Besòs River and supplies part of the Barcelona population. Another DWP is planned in La Llagosta, which will take water indirectly from Besòs River after riverbank filtration. Alternatively, treated wastewater can be released into the river, which may affect the ecological flow of the river basin or downstream recreation.

3. Co-Creation Process to Create Zero-Pollution Strategies

To create a viable strategy for enabling reclaimed water use that considers the presence of micro-contaminants, a system view is needed on both the problem(s) and potential solutions. For this purpose, PROMISCES organized a co-creation process with local stakeholders in the Besòs River Basin. The first of two interactive, co-creation workshops took place on 28 November 2023 at CBT headquarters in Granollers, Spain with a diverse group of more than 25 external stakeholders. The goals of this in-person workshop, as decided by the participating stakeholders at the beginning of the workshop, were to (Figure 1):

- Share knowledge among stakeholders
- Identify barriers and accompanying solutions for wastewater reuse
- Establish quality criteria for reclaimed water
- Develop an immediate, concrete action plan

Figure 1. Structure and agenda of the 1st workshop

The second workshop took place on the 5th of March, 2024 and was held online. This event was attended by more than 38 external stakeholders from which 1/3 of the attendees had also participated in the 1st co-creation workshop. The main objective of the workshop was to link identified solutions with the enablers to develop a system-wide strategy to support the use of reclaimed water for agricultural irrigation in the Besòs River Basin. Specifically, the following aspects were discussed to further develop a strategy (Figure 2):

- How can the chosen solutions make use of the identified enablers? Review the connection and discussion on public perception.
- What actors are involved in the solutions and who has the responsibility for implementation?
- Who is responsible for financing the solutions and where does this financial support come from?
- In what order should actions be taken when part of a comprehensive strategy?

Figure 2. Structure and agenda of the 2nd workshop

4. 1st Co-creation Workshop, Granollers, Spain 2023

4.1 Workshop Part 1: Exploring the Problem

In the first part of the co-creation workshop, we discussed the results from the [preliminary survey](#) (available only in Catalan) to identify concerns and relevant aspects from the participants related to the use of reclaimed water. These aspects and concerns can be grouped in the following themes:

Public health

- Lack of quantification of public health risk derived of the use of reclaimed water
- What (chronic/systemic) risks are deemed acceptable?

Environmental

- Global presence of pollution/microcontaminants, not only present in water sources
- Point source contamination; lack of knowledge of presence of PMT in WWTPs

Technical

- Monitoring of PMTs of emerging contaminants is a barrier

Social

- Acceptance of water reuse
- Communication of risks reaching society/users
- Society's perception that freshwater should be "free" is seen as limiting

Financial

- Lack of funding for water treatment investment
- Who pays (for the use), and what happens to the one who pollutes?

Governance

- Public health and water management are not integrated
- Lack of political will to take action
- Transparency between administrations needed

Legislative

- There are no limit values
- Reduce/Manage substances at the origin (industry/agriculture); substances not included in industrial discharge limits

4.2 Workshop Part 2: Barriers & Enablers

4.2.1 Identifying Barriers

For each of the relevant aspect themes, barriers and enablers were identified in a world café setting (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Pictures from the world cafés, during which barriers and enablers were identified.

The output from the world cafés is presented in Table 1 per theme. The barriers indicated in bold were prioritised afterwards (see below).

Table 1. Barriers and enablers pertaining to the use of reclaimed water. The bolded text are the prioritized barriers.

BARRIERS	ENABLERS
Environmental health	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drought (overexploitation + prioritizing other uses) • Inability to quantify benefit <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Water footprint ○ Economic ○ Tourism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protection of water bodies • Regenerated water master plans • Increased controls • New studies and projects • Decrease in resource (quality)
Public health	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current regulations do not contemplate PMTs • Lack of context and knowledge • Lack of systematization in procedures • To whom lies the responsibility • Perception and communication • Lack of standardization/monitoring • Governance within ACA (Catalan Water Agency) / health • Transparency in having data • Uniform legislation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New directive for wastewater (draft proposal) • The current water quality • Drought • Existing studies and experiences / R+D+I • Risk management plans / Risk Assessment • Inadequate legislation
Social	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negative perception • Lack of knowledge / misinformation • Political mistrust • Sensational media • Stakeholders • Lack of knowledge of water sources • Increase in tariffs (resulting from drought) • Water not perceived as a priority (origin) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drought • Administration and operators • Technical media communication • Research projects • Increase in tariffs (optimizing resource use) • Avoiding excessive alarmism
Technical	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online instrumentation (real time monitoring) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drought • Elimination efficiency

BARRIERS	ENABLERS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verification control • High cost of water treatment technologies • Selectivity • The generation of by-products resulting from wastewater treatment (e.g., metabolites from AOP, Advanced Oxidation Process or brines/concentrates from separation processes) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Successful demonstration cases • Existing online technologies • IT tools (AI, databases, etc.) + • R + D + I (Research + Development + Innovation) • Traceability
Financial, Legislative, Governance	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of funding • Decision making is slow • Current legislation does not favour quick actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Bureaucracy ○ Not very realistic / operational • Governance that comes from top to bottom instead from bottom to top • Availability of monitoring equipment for operators (outdated prices) • Lack of a specific list / PMT indicators with limits • Maintenance (cost) of treatment equipment (UV, RO, etc.). • Reused water is not considered as part of the supply in governance • Organization and communication between administrations, e.g., health and water management • No agreed political agreements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drought (a new drought) possibility to contain/advance • Examples of success cases at home (e.g., Aguas Industriales de Tarragona, S.A.) • Corporate image of companies (CSR - Corporate Social Responsibility) • Point source industrial discharges (e.g., 1,4-dioxane) <li style="text-align: center;">↑ ↓ • Fines for non-compliance (industry + operators) • Technical capacity of the involved agencies (R+D, management). • European projects • National-level projects • River basin plan → distribution management • Basin Action Plan (PDAR) for the Besòs Basin • Basin Action Plan (PDAR) for the Metropolitan Area (in process) -> Costa Brava • Common legislation at the European level

4.2.2 Prioritizing Barriers

After creating the lists in the world café, the participants voted on the priority of the barriers (see Figure 4). The most important barriers are indicated in bold in Table 1 above and are listed below.

Figure 4. The workshop participants used red, yellow and green stickers to identify the barriers that should be prioritized. Red means highest priority.

The majority of the most urgent/important barriers were identified from the public health discussion, although they were not only related to public health. For example, a lack of cooperation and division of responsibility between the public health and water sector is also related to governance and/or legislation. The complete list of prioritized barriers is as follows:

- | | |
|--|-----------------------------|
| 1. Lack of knowledge about the risk in public health | [public health/social] |
| 2. The current organization of the administration (reclaimed water, drinking water, and public health). Who is responsible? | [public health/governance] |
| 3. Lack of a specific list of PMTs or indicators, with quality limits. Current legislation does not consider PMT substances. | [public health/legislative] |
| 4. Lack of funding | [financial/social] |
| 5. Cost of water | [financial/social] |
| 6. The cost of treatment technology is not always clear or comparable. | [technical/financial] |
| 7. Generation of by-products (concentrates, oxidation, etc.). Lack of knowledge about the by-products of Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOP). | [technical] |
| 8. Perception (and communication) of PMTs to the general public. Lack of knowledge and the presence of misinformation. | [public health/social] |

4.3 Workshop Part 3: Identifying Solutions

4.3.1 Brainstorming of solutions

For the most important barriers, the next step was to identify solutions. This started with a 'brain-dump' by the participants, in which they provided as many solutions as possible for each of the identified barriers (see Figure 5). The results of this brainstorm by the participants are indicated in Table 2.

Figure 5. The participants used sticky notes to brainstorm solutions for the 8 prioritized barriers.

Table 2. Solutions proposed by the participants for the 8 prioritized barriers. The selected solutions are **bolded**.

Financial	
1.	<p>Barrier: Lack of funding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assign responsibility for each investment • Include PMT concentrations in the effluent fee • Prioritize the funding of the whole water cycle management in the budget (e.g., for developing Regenerated Water Master Plans by basin, hiring specialized technicians) • Add the cost of regeneration to the supply fee
2.	<p>Barrier: Cost of water</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variable prices according to the context; increase in emergency situations • Variable price based on the quality of regenerated water (with intended use for each quality) • Variable price based on consumption and/or incentives for savings • Penalties / External public audits
Legislation	
3.	<p>Barrier: Lack of a specific list of PMT or indicators, with quality limits. Current legislation does not consider PMT substances.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish working groups similar to the one in Baix Llobregat • Agile updating of the list • Create a model/methodology/procedure to decide which PMTs should be considered on a case-by-case basis • Systematize decision-making • Include substances explicitly in legislation
Governance	

<p>4. Barrier: The current organization of administration (regenerated water, drinking water, and public health). Who bears the responsibility.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shared responsibility • Creation of a joint entity/unit for the comprehensive management of water • Create groups/round tables for each case study / shared responsibility <p>5. Barrier: Lack of knowledge about the risk to public health.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantify the risk to human health for each water reuse case • Transparency • Protocol to estimate risks to human health / methodology for risk assessment • Research on toxicity, presence, risks, etc.
Technical
<p>6. Barrier: Cost of treatment technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control of discharges at the source (monitoring origin of industrial pollution) • Establish & communicate performance indicators (e.g. energy/m3) • Investment in natural treatments (nature-based, biological), simpler and cheaper <p>7. Barrier: Generation of by-products (concentrates, oxidation, etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More R+D for by-product recovery, research on redox processes • More collectors for brines
Social
<p>8. Barrier: Perception and communication (society)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General communication with audiovisual campaigns. • Targeted and adapted communication for each type of user. • Promoting success cases. • Communication professionals in each of the operators and water management administrations. • Dissemination of the cost of each existing treatment.

4.3.2 Selecting priority actions

After the 'brain-dump' round, the identified solutions were grouped, discussed and prioritized in a plenary setting. Based on this discussion, the following priority actions were identified:

1. Prioritize financing for water cycle management in budgets (e.g., for developing Regenerated Water Master Plans by basin, hiring specialized technicians)
2. Variable price for water based on consumption and/or incentives for savings
3. Agile updating of the PMT-list
4. Include substances explicitly in legislation
5. Create groups/round tables for each case study / shared responsibility
6. Protocol to estimate risks to human health / methodology for risk assessment
7. Research on toxicity, presence, risks, etc.
8. Control of discharges at the source (monitoring origin of industrial pollution)
9. Establish & communicate performance indicators (e.g. energy/m3)
10. More R+D for by-product recovery, research on redox processes
11. Targeted and adapted communication for each type of user
12. Communication professionals in each of the operators and water management administrations

4.4 Reflection after 1st Workshop

The first workshop made clear that an immediate action plan is needed, and priority actions for this were identified. During the workshop, it was mentioned several times that the absence of the public health authority had an influence on the discussion. Most notably, there was less focus on the health concerns involved with reclaimed water, especially for potable use.

Two outcomes may also be taken up further. First, the workshop's initial focus was on the use of reclaimed water for agriculture. During the workshop, it was brought up that it was generally accepted to use reclaimed water for agriculture and the need was expressed to develop a strategy for the use of reclaimed water for potable use. The question is whether this need for and focus on potable usage can be turned into an argument for proactive treatment (the reasoning being that for potable usage, safety is of even greater importance), thereby overcoming difficulties in decision making and creating shared responsibility. The idea of linking monitoring to a forum with stakeholders with shared responsibility can be particularly important here: the required treatment of PMTs could initially be less strict and therefore less costly, while stakeholders commit themselves to improve treatment if monitoring shows the need for it.

Secondly, public perception is considered very important, but in two respects: possible risks of water reuse can be exaggerated, while the public's expectation that water is safe (e.g. pharmaceuticals in the water are not an issue) may result in a lack of trust. Could communication about PMT presence and treatment help to increase the political will for researching and implementing proper treatment technologies?

5. 2nd Co-creation Workshop, Online 2024

5.1 Workshop Part 1: Reflect on 1st Workshop Outcomes

In the first part of the co-creation workshop, the participants were reminded of the outcomes from the 1st workshop. The relevant key takeaways were shared and identified as:

- Economic, social and governance boundary conditions are needed to successfully implement (direct/PMT) solutions
- A barrier can require an action / solution in a different part of the system
- Different barriers can have the same solution or require the same boundary condition
- Public perception of the reclaimed water is considered important

These takeaways highlight the importance of cross-sectoral communication, and the integration of all actors for a successful implementation. Additionally, the role of the stakeholders in the 2nd workshop was taken one step further, from passive observers of barriers and challenges, to active participants in the solutions they identified as priorities and the leaders of the actions that could support a successful implementation.

The goal for this second workshop was formulated taking into consideration this active role, bringing together interested stakeholders to develop an immediate and concrete action plan. Therefore, the co-creation process was divided into two sections, "order of the actions" and "towards a concrete action plan". In the first part of the activities, the stakeholders were encouraged to look at what actions were needed and how they were connected. Meanwhile, in the second part of the process, the participants were encouraged to identify what actions they could perform and their feasibility.

Participants discussed these questions via an online [Miro Board](#). The following sections summarize the outputs.

5.2 Workshop Part 2: Order of the Actions

Building off of the 12 identified priority actions from the 1st workshop (see Section “Selecting priority actions”), the stakeholders were divided into three breakout groups and asked to discuss and illustrate:

- How the identified actions are connected
- Whether the implementation of one action facilitates the implementation of another
- Which actions are dependent on each other
- How the actions in the end contribute to enabling the use of reclaimed water

The output of each group can be found in Figure 6, Figure 7, and Figure 8.

Figure 6. Order of the actions - Breakout Group 1.

Figure 7. Order of the actions – Breakout Group 2.

Figure 8. Order of the actions - Breakout Group 3.

5.3 Workshop Part 3: Implementation & Roadmap

To produce a concrete plan of action, the stakeholders were tasked with prioritizing solutions and identifying potential synergies that would trigger a “snowball effect”, meaning facilitating the implementation of other following actions. To achieve this, they were asked to consider the following questions:

- What can I (my organization) do to help realize/implement this solution (these solutions)?
- Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?
- How feasible is the solution?
- Is this solution somehow already being supported? If so, how or through what mechanism?

As can be seen in Figure 9, the top three categories that were prioritized as solutions correspond to social, safety assessment and governance. Only one group suggested a new solution (Figure 9, solution 14), which addresses the financial aspect of implementing treatment technologies. This new solution also uses shared responsibility as a basis for solving the water crisis in the Besòs River region.

Figure 9. Comparison of prioritization of solutions between the different groups.

Table 3 lists the active role the stakeholders could play for each solution as well as the information of who they identified as partners to support the solution. The table also includes drivers for the solution's implementation. The solution that had overwhelming positive responses in feasibility as well as in willingness to participate was in the Social category and alluded to *co-responsibility by creating working groups/round tables for each case study*. The next solution with mostly positive responses regarding participation was in the Safety Assessment category, calling for the *research on toxicity, presence, risks of PM(T)s*. Although this was classified as medium feasibility, many of the participating stakeholders were willing to perform the necessary studies and collaborate with each other. The main constraint for the implementation of this solution can be the financial aspect of funding such studies, which can be costly, require longer periods of time and are limited to the stakeholders that can perform research. Finally, the solutions which had the least responses and were identified as low and medium feasibility were related to the Governance category; the first being *variable pricing depending on consumption and/or savings incentives*, and the second, *financing WWTP treatments through co-responsibility*. Interestingly, both these solutions are centered around the cost and financing of the treatment processes and who is responsible for paying any perceived extra cost surrounding implementing extra treatment steps for irrigational water reuse.

Table 3. When participants were asked “What can I (my organization) do to help realize/implement this solution(s)?” they were asked to also consider how feasible the action was. They were asked to classify their responses using the following colors: highly feasible = green, medium feasibility = yellow, and low feasibility = red.

1.- Create working groups/round tables for each case study (Social)	
Aj. Granollers	Conversation with agents involved and participation in the tables. Search for places to do rehearsals.
Aigües de Barcelona	- We can contribute to the Llobregat experience. - Be proactive in the creation and participation of working groups (AB).
Sorigué	can participate in working groups.
IRTA	can contribute its experience in irrigation management with this type of water
ASPCAT	- Actively participate in WGs - Participation in technical groups
OdR	Share the vision of the agricultural side, user
Barcelona Regional	Organization, dynamism and monitoring of the implementation of the agreements
EURECAT	Organize and energize working groups
CBT	- Provide the tools for the creation of round tables - Provide information to working groups
IDAEA-CSIC	Contribute knowledge about PMTs
AMB	
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agricultural sector, industrial sector, administration, regenerated water users, operators, ACA, local authority - Media, NGOs or already sensitized groups - To create different working groups, different types of profile will be needed: technical, legal, health, communication, production technicians of the affected industries, politicians, end users, etc. 	
Is this solution already supported somehow? If so, how or by what mechanism?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research projects - Drought - Success stories - Existing studies and experiences - R+D+I 	
2.-Prioritize in the budget the financing of all water cycle management (Governance)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	Prioritize investments based on health risk and climate change criteria (AB).
Sorigué	
IRTA	can participate in projects providing the vision of the end user of water in agriculture
ASPCAT	
OdR	
Barcelona Regional	Support administrations
EURECAT	
CBT	Apply for Grants
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	Master Plans
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gencat, ACA, European Sources are the ones who provide financing - ACA - Private companies - Competent administrations 	

- Research groups	
Is this solution already supported somehow? If so, how or by what mechanism?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Drought - Decrease in resources - Fines for non-compliance (industry + operators) - Rate increase (optimization of resource use) 	
3.-Research on toxicity, presence, risks, etc. (Safety assessment)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	Study the presence of PMT in resources and treatments, risk assessment towards the population (AB).
Sorigué	facilitators of research as WWTP operators and participants in R+D projects. Specifically, for PROMISCES, we are the operators of Montornés.
IRTA	
ASPCAT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - collaboration with research centers - Participation with groups investigation of the presence and risk assessment of PMTs
OdR	
Barcelona Regional	
EURECAT	Research on toxicity and AOPs
CBT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work together with research centers - Carry out more studies of the presence of PMT in the Besòs Tordera basin to prioritize the future list
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The operators, ACA and research groups (ASPCAT) - Research groups (AB) - Universities - Sorigué needs research organizations (Eurecat, IRTA, IDAEA-CSIC...), in fact we already collaborate on many projects 	
Is this solution already supported somehow? If so, how or by what mechanism?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Drought - Research Projects - Technical capacity of the agencies involved (R&D, management) - IT tools (AI, databases, etc.) 	
4.-Control of discharges at the source (surveillance of the source of industrial pollution) (Treatment/Monitoring)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	Notify the relevant administration of discharges detected in the control of our resources (AB).
Sorigué	can facilitate the control of discharges at the treatment plants we operate
IRTA	
ASPCAT	
OdR	
Barcelona Regional	Support administrations
EURECAT	Spill detection technology
CBT	Carry out random checks at the source according to the type of industry to do a general scan of the source of the PMT and consult with experts on alternative treatments at the source.
IDAEA-CSIC	Perform analysis

	Identification, prioritization and monitoring of emerging pollutants in the case study.
AMB	
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participation of the WWTPs (e.g. for sample collection), collaborators for experiments on the elimination and capture of these pollutants in crops - Local Authority - ACA - Operator - Private Companies - Ministry - Industry - Research groups (R&D, universities) 	
Is this solution already supported somehow? If so, how or by what mechanism?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Drought - More controls - Point discharges of industrial origin (e.g. 1,4-dioxane) 	
5.-More R&D for by-product recovery, research on redox processes (Treatment)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	Study new potabilization/purification treatments, and optimize existing ones in order to minimize the formation of by-products (AB)
Sorigué	
IRTA	
ASPCAT	Collaboration with research centers
OdR	
Barcelona Regional	
EURECAT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - R&D in the field of treatment, management of by-products - Have studies and pilot experiences of treatments and technologies - Research on toxicity and AOPs
CBT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work together with research centers - Participate in the validation of pilot plants / new technologies in our facilities
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Operators and administrations in the field of water to address the different needs they may have - Universities - Companies - R&D center 	
Is this solution already supported somehow? If so, how or by what mechanism?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Drought - Success stories - Existing studies and experiences - R+D+I 	
6.-Include PMT substances explicitly in legislation (Governance)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	**Anticipate the control of PMTs not included in the legislation (AB)
Sorigué	
IRTA	
ASPCAT	do more health risk assessment of PMTs. Consult with other CCAA and countries that have more experience
	Contacts with competent ministry

OdR	
Barcelona Regional	
EURECAT	Substance identification and risk analysis methodology
CBT	Facilitate case studies such as the case of Montornès
IDAEA-CSIC	<p>**Make recommendations on the substances to be included</p> <p>Pooling of the PMT research studies of the different local bodies within the same basin or inter-basins to share a list of detected PMTs and prioritize substances or map hot spots.</p>
AMB	dumping regulation
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ACA - Collaboration with the different local bodies – operators - Ministry 	
Is this solution already supported somehow? If so, how or by what mechanism?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Drought - Existing studies and experiences - R+D+I - Point discharges of industrial origin (e.g. 1,4-dioxane) 	
7.-Communication directed and adapted to each type of user (Social)	
Aj. Granollers	We can collaborate on communication
Aiguës de Barcelona	Work on the communicative part aimed at the different uses of regenerated water, especially from the acceptance side
Sorigué	
IRTA	
ASPCAT	Health risk communication
OdR	Organize transfer and training days
Barcelona Regional	
EURECAT	Scientific communication
CBT	Provide information to the industrial and agricultural sector
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reference bodies that can give a reassuring message - ACA - General 	
Is this solution already supported somehow? If so, how or by what mechanism?	
<i>No response</i>	
8.-Risk estimation protocol for human health / risk assessment methodology (Security Assessment / Governance)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aiguës de Barcelona	
Sorigué	
IRTA	Can participate in the effect of the use of this water on the soil and crops
ASPCAT	
OdR	
Barcelona Regional	
EURECAT	
CBT	
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	

Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?	
<i>No response</i>	
Is this solution already supported somehow? If so, how or by what mechanism?	
<i>No response</i>	
9.-Communication professionals in each of the water management operators and administrations (Social)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	
Sorigué	
IRTA	
ASPCAT	Health risk communication
OdR	Organize transfer and training days
Barcelona Regional	
EURECAT	Scientific communication
CBT	Provide information to the industrial and agricultural sector
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ACA - General 	
Is this solution already supported somehow? If so, how or by what mechanism?	
<i>No response</i>	
10.-Agile PMT list update process (Governance)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	
Sorigué	
IRTA	
ASPCAT	Do more health risk assessment of PMTs. Consult with other CCAA and countries that have more experience
OdR	
Barcelona Regional	
EURECAT	Substance identification and risk analysis methodology Support through ecosystem and human health risk assessments in order to draw up the list
CBT	Facilitate case studies such as the case of Montornès
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	Dumping regulation
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ACA 	
Is this solution already supported somehow? If so, how or by what mechanism?	
<i>No response</i>	
11.-Variable price depending on consumption and/or savings incentives (Governance)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	
Sorigué	
IRTA	
ASPCAT	
OdR	
Barcelona Regional	Support administrations
EURECAT	Spill detection technology

CBT	
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Authority - ACA - Operator - Private Companies 	
Is this solution already supported somehow? If so, how or by what mechanism?	
<i>No response</i>	
12.-Financing WWTP treatments through co-responsibility (New Wastewater Directive)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	
Sorigué	
IRTA	
ASPCAT	
OdR	
Barcelona Regional	Support administrations
EURECAT	
CBT	Apply subsidies
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	Master plans
Who else is needed? Who can I collaborate with?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ACA - Private companies 	
Is this solution already supported somehow? If so, how or by what mechanism?	
<i>No response</i>	

6. Conclusion

The structure of the workshops resulted in an action list of how to deal with PM(T) substances during the reuse of water within the Besòs River Basin. Going a bit further, the stakeholders identified the actions that form the first step towards the safe and cost-effective reuse of wastewater for irrigation. The first step identified by the stakeholders is the creation of working groups/roundtables where all sectors of society can participate and offer their knowledge/concerns to create a communal strategy. The stakeholder workshop itself and its participants can be seen as a starting point for such a working group.

The stakeholders all agreed that wastewater reuse for agriculture should be an integral part of the water management strategy in the Besòs River Basin, even placing a heavy importance on potable reuse to be considered. However, the questions of who pays and how much are still open. Consequently, actions related to financing of the treatment for PM(T)s are seen as less feasible.

For many of the solutions, there currently is no institutional support for their implementation, highlighting the need for policymakers to participate in working groups at the local level. Beyond policymakers, the solutions and the implementation support offered by the participants highlights the need for cross-sectoral collaboration and communication in the Besòs River Basin to successfully address water scarcity. This co-creation workshop process serves as an exercise in this “system-wide” approach on which the local stakeholders can build moving forward.

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**Preventing Recalcitrant Organic Mobile Industrial chemicals
for Circular Economy in the soil-sediment-water System**

Catalan version

Catalan translation of the summary of two Co-creation Stakeholder Workshops for the Besòs River Basin (CS3)

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1. Introducció

Durant dos tallers de co-creació, representants locals i regionals d'entitats de serveis d'aigua, ajuntaments, empreses d'enginyeria, instituts de recerca i del sector agrari es van reunir a Granollers, Espanya, per discutir les opcions i limitacions de la reutilització agrícola a la zona del riu Besòs. La reutilització de les aigües residuals és necessària per fer front als efectes del canvi climàtic als països mediterranis i és una ruta important cap a una economia circular més àmplia. Tanmateix, si les solucions de tractament d'aigua ofereixen aigua recuperada segura i rendible depèn de molts factors. Per tant, el projecte de recerca de la UE PROMISCES va organitzar aquests dos tallers de co-creació de parts interessades. En el document següent es descriu el procés, els resultats inicials i els resultats obtinguts a partir de la 1a i 2a reunions de taller.

2. Antecedents

2.1 Situació actual

L'Agència Catalana de l'Aigua (ACA), tal i com indica al seu Pla de gestió del districte de conca fluvial de Catalunya per al període 2022-2027, vol promoure la reutilització de l'aigua, entre d'altres, a la conca del riu Besòs per mitigar les restriccions d'aigua imposades a causa dels períodes de sequera cada cop més freqüents i combatre la creixent escassetat d'aigua. Amb aquesta finalitat, 64 municipis que treballen conjuntament al Consorci Besòs Tordera (CBT) van iniciar a l'any 2018 el Pla Director d'Aigües Regenerades (PDAR). Aquest pla valora les necessitats d'aigua regenerada a les conques dels rius Besòs i Tordera, i proposa la construcció d'una sèrie d'Estacions de Regeneració d'Aigua (ERA) i infraestructures de transport per satisfer la demanda urbana, agrícola, industrial i ambiental d'aigua.

L'any 2022, aproximadament el 95% de l'aigua de la conca del riu provenia dels abocaments de plantes de tractament d'aigües residuals (EDAR). Part d'aquestes descàrregues podrien ser utilitzades per a reg agrícola per alleujar el consum d'aigua superficial i potable. Per a la reutilització agrícola, caldria eliminar contaminants emergents, com substàncies químiques específiques o residus de medicaments procedents tant de fonts industrials com domèstiques. Especialment, en les últimes dècades ha anat creixent la preocupació per les substàncies químiques que no es degraden (persistents; P), que es poden dispersar fàcilment pel medi ambient (mòbils; M), i que poden perjudicar els organismes (tòxiques; T), conegudes com a PMT. El disseny actual de les ERA no contempla a priori l'eliminació de substàncies PMT, ja que les seves limitacions no es troben regulades i existeix una manca de coneixement al voltant de les millors tècniques per a la seva eliminació. No obstant, això podria arribar a ser necessari si l'aigua s'ha d'utilitzar amb finalitats agrícoles (reg) per evitar que les concentracions de substàncies PMT que es troben en els cultius superin els nivells de seguretat per a la salut humana i ambiental. Les futures regulacions previstes poden exigir que algunes de les substàncies PMT s'eliminin de l'aigua regenerada per a usos agrícoles i altres usos.

2.2 Abordatge dels riscos de les substàncies PMT per a l'ús agrícola en el Pla Director d'Aigües Regenerades

Com a part del projecte de recerca finançat per la Unió Europea, PROMISCES, el Consorci Besòs Tordera (CBT) amb Eurecat i IDAEA-CSIC col·laboren per provar diverses tecnologies de tractament d'aigua utilitzant la infraestructura de l'Estació Depuradora d'Aigües Residuals (EDAR) de Montornès

del Vallès i l'Urban River Lab. Aquest cas d'estudi investiga si aquestes tecnologies proporcionen solucions econòmiques i viables per eliminar microcontaminants de manera que l'aigua tractada pugui ser aplicada de manera segura per a reg agrícola. Es busquen solucions econòmiques mitjançant combinacions híbrides de tecnologies.

Durant l'any 2022, es van identificar uns 20 compostos químics orgànics d'origen industrial en el corrent d'aigües residuals que entra a Montornès del Vallès. Tot i que l'origen d'aquests químics és difícil d'identificar, el corrent d'aigües residuals que entra en aquesta EDAR té una procedència del 60% industrial i 40% municipal/domèstic. En el cas d'estudi, les aigües residuals a la sortida de la depuradora són tractades mitjançant un procés d'oxidació electroquímica avançada (EAOP) combinat amb un aigüamoll construït. L'aigua tractada s'aplica per al reg de cultius agrícoles destinats a consum humà, en aquest cas enciams. Per determinar quins nivells de concentració de contaminants poden quedar en l'aigua destinada a ús agrícola, es realitzarà una avaluació de riscos per al consum directe (cultius) i indirecte (farratge per al bestiar). Basant-se en aquests resultats, es redactaran recomanacions per als agricultors per a la selecció de cultius i millors pràctiques agrícoles que minimitzin la transferència de microcontaminants a les parts comestibles dels cultius.

2.3 Perspectives i impactes

Els resultats del cas d'estudi seran interessants per a tota la regió del riu Besòs, ja que es preveu un nombre de plantes de reutilització d'aigua (ERA). El disseny d'aquestes ERA es basa en tecnologies de tractament convencionals, que no tenen en compte compostos químics com els microcontaminants o contaminants emergents. De manera més àmplia, l'experiència amb tecnologies de tractament podria ser abordada pels membres del Catalan Water Partnership (CWP). La construcció de la primera ERA de la conca començarà al llarg de l'any 2024.

Atès que les escassetats d'aigua poden ser severes, l'aigua residual tractada també pot ser utilitzada per la indústria, els municipis (p. ex. neteja de carrers), propietaris de camps de golf o fins i tot plantes de tractament d'aigua potable (ETAP). Actualment, només hi ha una planta de tractament d'aigua potable aigües avall de l'EDAR Montornès del Vallès i l'Urban River Lab (ETAP Besòs), que tracta aigua subterrània barrejada amb aigua del riu Besòs, i subministra aigua de boca a part de la població de Barcelona. Està prevista una altra ETAP a La Llagosta, que agafarà aigua del riu Besòs després d'una infiltració a través de la zona de ribera. Alternativament, l'aigua residual tractada s'aboca al riu, la qual cosa pot afectar el cabal ecològic de la conca del riu o la recreació aigües avall.

3. Procés de co-creació per crear estratègies de contaminació zero

Per crear una estratègia viable per permetre l'ús de l'aigua recuperada que tingui en compte la presència de microcontaminants, es necessita una visió del sistema tant del problema (s) com de les possibles solucions. Amb aquesta finalitat, PROMISCES va organitzar un procés de co-creació amb els agents locals de la conca del riu Besòs. El primer de dos tallers interactius de co-creació va tenir lloc el 28 de novembre de 2023 a la seu de CBT a Granollers, Espanya, amb un grup divers de més de 25 grups d'interès externs. Els objectius d'aquest taller presencial, tal com van decidir les parts interessades participants a l'inici del taller, eren (vegeu la Figura 1):

- Compartir coneixements entre els participants

- Identificar barreres i les solucions associades a la reutilització d'aigües residuals
- Establir criteris de qualitat per a l'aigua regenerada
- Desenvolupar un pla d'acció immediat i concret

Figura 1. Estructura i agenda del 1r taller.

El segon taller va tenir lloc el 5 de març de 2024 i es va realitzar en línia. Aquest acte va comptar amb la participació de més de 38 agents externs dels quals 1/3 dels assistents també havien participat en el 1r taller de cocreació. L'objectiu principal del taller era vincular les solucions identificades amb els facilitadors per desenvolupar una estratègia de tot el sistema per donar suport a l'ús de l'aigua regenerada per al reg agrícola a la conca del riu Besòs. Concretament, es van discutir els aspectes següents per desenvolupar una estratègia (Figura 2):

- Com poden les solucions escollides fer ús dels facilitadors identificats? Revisar la connexió i la discussió sobre la percepció pública.
- Quins actors estan implicats en les solucions i qui té la responsabilitat de la implementació?
- Qui és el responsable de finançar les solucions i d'on prové aquest suport econòmic?
- En quin ordre s'han d'actuar quan formen part d'una estratègia integral?

Figura 2. Estructura i agenda del 2n taller

4. 1r Taller de Cocreació, Granollers, Espanya 2023

4.1 Taller Part 1: Plantejament del Problema

En la primera part del taller de co-creació, vam discutir els resultats de [l'enquesta preliminar](#) per identificar preocupacions i aspectes rellevants dels participants relacionats amb l'ús d'aigua regenerada. Aquests aspectes i preocupacions es poden agrupar en els següents temes:

Salut Pública

- Manca de quantificació del risc per a la salut pública derivat de l'ús d'aigua regenerada
- Quins riscos (crònics/sistèmics) són considerats acceptables?

Medi Ambient

- Presència global de contaminació/microcontaminants, no només en els recursos hídrics
- Contaminació de font puntual; falta de coneixement de la presència de PMT en EDAR

Tècnic

- El monitoratge de contaminants emergents és una barrera

Social

- Acceptació de la reutilització d'aigua
- Comunicació dels riscos que arriben a la societat/usuaris
- La percepció de la societat que l'aigua dolça ha de ser "gratuïta"

Financer

- Manca de finançament per a la inversió en tractament d'aigua
- Qui paga (per l'ús), i què passa amb el qui contamina?

Governança

- La salut pública i la gestió de l'aigua no estan integrades
- Manca de voluntat política per actuar
- Transparència entre administracions necessària

Legislatiu

- No hi ha valors límit
- Reduir/gestionar substàncies a l'origen (indústria/agricultura); substàncies no incloses en els límits de descàrrega industrial

4.2 Taller Part 2: Barreres & Facilitadors

4.2.1 Identificant Barreres

Per a cada un dels temes anteriors, es van identificar barreres i facilitadors en un ambient acollidor en el qual es van connectar, intencionadament, idees i perspectives en diverses rondes de conversa mitjançant petits grups de treball (vegeu la Figura 3).

Figura 3. Fotografies de la dinàmica de grups durant els quals es van identificar barreres i facilitadors.

Els resultats d'aquestes rondes de conversa es presenten a la Taula 1 per a cadascun dels temes. Les barreres indicades en negreta van ser prioritzades posteriorment (vegeu a continuació).

Taula 1. Barreres i facilitadors associades a l'ús d'aigua regenerada. El text en negreta són les barreres prioritzades.

BARRERS	FACILITADORS
Salut ambiental	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sequera (sobreexplotació + prioritzar altres usos) • Incapacitat de quantificar benefici <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Petjada hídrica - Econòmic - Turisme 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protecció de les masses d'aigua • Plans directors d'aigua regenerada • Augment dels controls • Nous estudis i projectes • Disminució del recurs (qualitat)
Salut pública	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reglament actual no contempla PMT • Falta context i coneixement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nova directiva per a aigües residuals i regenerada (esborrany) • La qualitat de l'aigua actual

BARRERS	FACILITADORS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manca de sistematització en els procediments • A qui li cau la responsabilitat • Percepció i comunicació • Manca monitorització • Governança dins de l'ACA (Agència Catalana de l'Aigua) i amb Dept. Salut • Transparència de dades • Legislació unificada 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sequera • Estudis i experiències existents / R+ D+ i • Plans gestió risc / avaluacions de risc químic • Legislació <u>uniforme</u>
Societat	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percepció negativa • Desconeixement / desinformació • Desconfiança política • Mitjans comunicació sensacionalista • Desconeixement fonts d'aigua • Increment de tarifes (derivat de sequera) • Aigua no percebuda com a prioritària (origen) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sequera • Administració i operadors • Mitjans comunicació tècnics • Projectes d'investigació • Increment de tarifes (s'optimitza l'ús del recurs) • Evitar alarmisme excessiu
Tecnologies	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instrumentació on-line (monitoratge) • Control de verificació • Cost tecnològic tractament • Selectivitat • Subproductes originats en processos d'oxidació avançada (AOP) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sequera • Rendiment d'eliminació • Casos d'èxit • Tecnologia on-line existent • Eines IT (AI , bases dades, etc.) • R + D + i • Traçabilitat
Finançament, Legislació, Governança	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manca de finançament • Presa decisions és lenta • Legislació actual no afavoreix accions ràpides <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ burocràcia ○ poc realista / operativa • Governança que Ve de dalt a baix en lloc de baix a dalt • Disponibilitat equips monitoreig per part operadors (preus analítiques alts) • Manca lliste concreta / indicadors de PMTs amb limits • Manteniment (cost) equipos tractament (UV, RO, etc.) • AR no es considera com a abastament en governança • Organització comunicació entre adminstracions → p.e. salut i gesio aigua • No acrods polítics consensuats (canvis colors) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sequera (una nova sequera) possibilitat de canviar / avançar • Exemple casos d'èxit a casa nostra (p.e. Aguas Industriales de Tarragona, S.A; AITASA) • Imatge corporativa empreses (RSC) • Abocaments industrials puntuals (p.e. diòxid) • ↑ • ↓ • multes per incompliments (indústria + operadors) • capacitat tècnica dels agends implicats (R+D, gestió) • Projectes europeus • Projectes a nivell nacional • Pla de conca → gestió de distriote • PDAR Conca Besòs • PDAR Àrea metropolitana (e procés) → Costa Brava • Legislació comuna a nivell europeu

4.2.2 Prioritzant Barreres

Després de crear les llistes en els debats, els participants van votar sobre la prioritat de les barreres (vegeu la Figura 4). Les barreres més importants estan indicades en negreta a la Taula 1 anterior i es llisten a continuació.

Figura 4. Els participants del taller van utilitzar adhesius vermells, grocs i verds per identificar les barreres que s'haurien de prioritzar. Vermell significa màxima prioritat.

La majoria de les barreres més urgents/importants es van identificar en l'àmbit de la salut pública, tot i que no estaven únicament relacionades amb la salut pública. Per exemple, manca de responsabilitat cooperació i repartiment de responsabilitats entre el sector de la salut pública i el sector de l'aigua també està relacionada amb la governança i/o legislació. La llista completa de barreres prioritzades és la següent:

- | | |
|---|----------------------------|
| 1. Manca de coneixement sobre el risc en salut pública que té l'ús de l'aigua regenerada | [salut pública/societat] |
| 2. L'organització actual de l'administració (aigua regenerada, aigua potable i salut pública). A qui li cau la responsabilitat. | [salut pública/governança] |
| 3. Manca de llista concreta de PMT o indicadors, amb límits de qualitat. Legislació actual no contempla substàncies PMT. | [salut pública/legal] |
| 4. Manca finançament | [finançament/societat] |
| 5. Cost de l'aigua | [finançament/societat] |
| 6. El cost de la tecnologia de tractament no sempre és clar ni comparable | [tècnic/finançament] |
| 7. Generació de subproductes (concentrats, oxidació, etc.). La manca de coneixement sobre els subproductes dels processos d'oxidació avançada (AOP) | [tècnic] |
| 8. Percepció (i comunicació) de la presència de PMTs al públic en general. La manca de coneixement i la desinformació. | [salut pública/societat] |

4.3 Taller Part 3: Identificar solucions

4.3.1 Pluja d'idees per a identificar solucions

Per a les barreres més importants, el següent pas va ser identificar solucions. Això va començar amb una pluja d'idees per part dels participants, els quals van proporcionar tantes solucions com va ser possible per a cadascuna de les barreres identificades (veure Figura 5). Els resultats d'aquesta pluja d'idees s'indiquen a la Taula 2.

Figura 5. Els participants van utilitzar notes adhesives per fer una pluja d'idees per donar solucions a les 8 barreres prioritzades.

Taula 2. Solucions proposades pels participants per a les 8 barreres prioritzades. Les solucions seleccionades estan en negra.

Finançament
<p>1. Barrera: Manca finançament</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Assignar responsable de cada inversió b. Incloure concentracions PMT en el cànon de sanejament c. Priorització finançament de la gestió dels cycle de l'aigua en els pressupostos del govern (p.e., per fer Plans Directors d'Aigua Regenerada per conca, contractar tècnics especialistes) d. Afegir en el cànon d'abastament el cost de la regeneració <p>2. Barrera: Cost de l'aigua</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Preus variables segons context b. Preu variable segons qualitat aigua regenerada (amb ús previst per a cadascuna de les qualitats) c. Preu variable segons consum i/o bonificacions per premiar l'estalvi d. Sancions / Auditories externes públiques
Legislació
<p>3. Barrera: Manca de llista concreta de PMT o indicadors, amb límits de qualitat. La legislació actual no contempla substàncies PMT.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crear equips de treball similars al del Baix Llobregat • Actualització àgil de la llista • Crear un model/metodologia/procediment per a decidir quins PMT s'han de tenir en compte cas per cas • Sistematitzar la presa de decisions • Incloure explícitament substàncies a la legislació
Governança
<p>4. Barrera: L'organització actual de l'administració (aigua regenerada, aigua potable i salut pública). A qui li cau la responsabilitat.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsabilitat compartida • Creació entitat/unitat conjunta per la gestió integral de l'aigua • Crear grups/taules rodones per a cada estudi de cas / responsabilitat compartida <p>5. Barrera: Manca de coneixement sobre el risc en salut pública de l'ús de l'aigua regenerada.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantificar el risc per a salut humana de cada cas de reutilització d'aigua • Transparència

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protocol per a estimar els riscos per a salut humana • Investigació sobre toxicitat, presència, riscos, etc.
Tecnologies
6. Barrera: Cost de la tecnologia tractament <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control abocaments en origen • Establir i comunicar indicadors de rendiment (p. ex., energia/m3) • Inversió de tractaments naturals (basats en la natura, biològics), més simples i barats 7. Barrera: Generació de subproductes (concentrats, oxidació, etc.) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Més R+D per a recuperació de subproductes, investigació processos redox • Més col·lectors
Societat
8. Barrera: Percepció i comunicació (societat). Manca de coneixement sobre el risc en salut pública <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comunicació generalista amb campanyes audiovisuals • Comunicació dirigida i adaptada per a cada tipus d'usuari • Potenciar els casos d'èxit • Professionals de la comunicació en cadascuna de les operadores i administracions que gestionen aigua • Disseminació del cost de cadascun dels tractaments existents

4.3.2 Selecció d'accions prioritàries

Després de la ronda de "pluja d'idees", les solucions identificades es van agrupar, discutir i prioritzar en un entorn plenari. Basant-nos en aquesta discussió, es van identificar les següents accions prioritàries:

1. Prioritzar el finançament per a la gestió del cicle de l'aigua en els pressupostos (per exemple, per desenvolupar Plans Directors d'Aigua Regenerada per conca, contractar tècnics especialitzats).
2. Preu variable basat en el consum i/o incentius per estalviar.
3. Actualització àgil de la llista PMT.
4. Incloure explícitament substàncies a la legislació
5. Crear grups/taules rodones per a cada estudi de cas / responsabilitat compartida
6. Protocol per estimar riscos per a la salut humana / metodologia per a l'avaluació del risc.
7. Recerca sobre toxicitat, presència, riscos, etc.
8. Control abocaments en origen
9. Establir i comunicar indicadors de rendiment (p. ex., energia/m3)
10. Més R+D per a la recuperació de subproductes, recerca sobre processos redox.
11. Comunicació dirigida i adaptada per a cada tipus d'usuari.
12. Professionals de la comunicació en cadascun dels operadors i administracions de gestió de l'aigua.

4.4 Reflexió després del 1r Taller

El taller va deixar clar que es necessita un pla d'acció immediat, i s'han identificat accions prioritàries per a això. El següent pas en la construcció d'aquest pla d'acció seria definir un cronograma i distribuir les tasques. En el proper taller i en futures discussions, s'ha d'implicar a les autoritats de salut pública. Durant el taller, es va mencionar diverses vegades que l'absència de l'autoritat de salut pública va influir en la discussió. Sobretot, hi va haver menys enfocament en les preocupacions de salut relacionades amb l'aigua regenerada, especialment per a ús potable.

També es poden considerar dues conclusions més. Primer, l'enfocament inicial del taller era sobre l'ús de l'aigua regenerada per a l'agricultura. Durant el taller, es va plantejar que era generalment acceptat utilitzar aigua regenerada per a l'agricultura i es va expressar la necessitat de desenvolupar una estratègia per a l'ús de l'aigua regenerada per a consum potable. La qüestió és si aquesta necessitat i enfocament en l'ús potable es pot convertir en un argument per a un tractament proactiu (raonant que per a l'ús potable, la seguretat és encara més important), superant així les dificultats en la presa de decisions i creant una responsabilitat compartida. La idea d'enllaçar la monitorització amb un fòrum amb parts interessades amb responsabilitat compartida pot ser particularment important aquí: el tractament requerit dels PMTs inicialment podria ser menys estricte i per tant menys costós, mentre que les parts interessades es comprometen a millorar el tractament si la monitorització mostra la necessitat.

En segon lloc, la percepció pública es considera molt important, però en dos vessants: els possibles riscos per a la salut pública de la reutilització de l'aigua es poden exagerar, mentre que l'expectativa pública que l'aigua és segura (per exemple, que els fàrmacs a l'aigua no són un problema), pot resultar en una falta de confiança. Podria la disseminació de la presència i el tractament dels PMT ajudar a augmentar la voluntat política per investigar i implementar tecnologies de tractament adequades?

5. 2n Taller de cocreació, Online 2024

5.1 Taller Part 1: Reflexionar sobre els resultats del 1r Taller

A la primera part del taller de co-creació, es va recordar als participants els resultats del 1r taller. Els punts clau rellevants es van compartir i es van identificar com:

- Es necessiten condicions de límit econòmiques, socials i de governança per implementar amb èxit solucions (directes/PMT).
- Una barrera pot requerir una acció/solució en una part diferent del sistema
- Diferents barreres poden tenir la mateixa solució o requerir la mateixa condició de límit
- Es considera important la percepció pública de l'aigua recuperada

Aquestes conclusions destaquen la importància de la comunicació intersectorial i la integració de tots els actors per a una implementació exitosa. A més, el paper dels grups d'interès en el 2n taller es va fer un pas més, des d'observadors passius de barreres i reptes, fins a participants actius en les solucions que van identificar com a prioritats i els líders de les accions que podrien donar suport a una implementació reeixida.

L'objectiu d'aquest segon taller es va formular tenint en compte aquest paper actiu, reunint les parts interessades per desenvolupar un pla d'acció immediat i concret. Per tant, el procés de cocreació es va dividir en dos apartats, "ordre de les accions" i "cap a un pla d'acció concret". En la primera part de les activitats, es va animar als interessats a mirar quines accions eren necessàries i com estaven connectades. Mentrestant, en la segona part del procés, es va animar als participants a identificar quines accions podien realitzar i la seva viabilitat.

Els participants van discutir aquestes preguntes a través d'un [Miro Board](#) en línia. Les seccions següents resumeixen les sortides.

5.2 Taller Part 2: Ordre de les Accions

A partir de les 12 accions prioritàries identificades al primer taller (vegeu la secció "Selecció d'accions prioritàries"), els grups d'interès es van dividir en tres grups i se'ls va demanar que debatin i il·lustressin:

- Com es connecten les accions identificades
- Si la implementació d'una acció facilita la realització d'una altra
- Quines accions depenen les unes de les altres
- Com les actuacions al final contribueixen a possibilitar l'ús de l'aigua regenerada

La sortida de cada grup es pot trobar a la Figura 6, la Figura 7 i la Figura 8.

Figura 6.Ordre de les accions - Grup Breakout 1.

Figura 7. Ordre de les accions – Grup Breakout 2.

Figura 8. Ordre de les accions - Grup Breakout 3.

5.3 Taller Part 3: Implementació i full de ruta

Per elaborar un pla d'acció concret, es va encarregar als grups d'interès prioritzar les solucions i identificar possibles sinergies que desencadenarien un "efecte bola de neu", és a dir, facilitar la implementació d'altres accions següents. Per aconseguir-ho, se'ls va demanar que reflexionessin sobre les següents preguntes:

- Què puc fer jo (la meua organització) per ajudar a realitzar/implementar aquesta solució (aquestes solucions)?
- Qui més es necessita? Amb qui puc col·laborar?
- Què tan factible és la solució?
- D'alguna manera ja s'admet aquesta solució? Si és així, com o mitjançant quin mecanisme?

Com es pot veure a la Figura 9, les tres categories principals que es van prioritzar com a solucions corresponen a l'avaluació social, de seguretat i governança. Només un grup va suggerir una nova solució (Figura 9, solució 14), que aborda l'aspecte financer de la implementació de tecnologies de tractament. Aquesta nova solució també utilitza la responsabilitat compartida com a base per resoldre la crisi de l'aigua a la comarca del riu Besòs.

Figura 9. Comparació de prioritació de solucions entre els diferents grups.

La Taula 3 enumera el paper actiu que podrien tenir les parts interessades per a cada solució, així com la informació de qui van identificar com a socis per donar suport a la solució. La taula també inclou els controladors per a la implementació de la solució. La solució que va tenir respostes positives aclaparadores tant en viabilitat com en voluntat de participació va ser en la categoria Social i va al·ludir a la coresponsabilitat mitjançant la creació de grups de treball/taules rodones per a cada cas pràctic. La següent solució amb respostes majoritàriament positives pel que fa a la participació va ser a la categoria d'avaluació de seguretat, que demanava la investigació sobre toxicitat, presència i riscos de PM(T). Tot i que es va classificar com a viabilitat mitjana, moltes de les parts interessades participants estaven disposades a realitzar els estudis necessaris i col·laborar entre elles. La principal limitació per a la implementació d'aquesta solució pot ser l'aspecte financer del finançament d'aquests estudis, que pot ser costós, requerir períodes de temps més llargs i limitar-se als grups d'interès que poden realitzar investigacions. Finalment, les solucions que van tenir menys respostes i van ser identificades com a viabilitat baixa i mitjana es van relacionar amb la categoria de Governança; la primera, la tarifa variable en funció dels incentius al consum i/o l'estalvi, i la segona, el finançament dels tractaments de les EDAR mitjançant la coresponsabilitat. Curiosament, ambdues solucions se centren en el cost i el finançament dels processos de tractament i qui és responsable de pagar qualsevol cost addicional percebut relacionat amb la implementació de passos addicionals de tractament per a la reutilització de l'aigua de reg.

Taula 3. Quan se'ls va preguntar als participants "Què puc fer jo (la meua organització) per ajudar a realitzar/implementar aquesta o aquestes solucions?" se'ls va demanar que també consideressin fins a quin punt era factible l'acció. Se'ls va demanar que classifiquessin les seves respostes utilitzant els colors següents: altament factible = verd, viabilitat mitjana = groc i baixa viabilitat = vermell.

1.- Crear grups de treball/taules rodones per a cada cas pràctic (Social)	
Aj. Granollers	Conversa amb els agents implicats i participació a les taules. Busca llocs per fer assajos
Aigües de Barcelona	- Podem contribuir a l'experiència del Llobregat - Ser proactiu en la creació i participació de grups de treball
Sorigué	poden participar en grups de treball
IRTA	pot aportar la seva experiència en la gestió del reg amb aquest tipus d'aigua
ASPCAT	- Participar activament en els GT - Participació en grups tècnics
OdR	Comparteix la visió del vessant agrícola, usuari
Barcelona Regional	Organització, dinamització i seguiment de l'execució dels convenis
EURECAT	Organitzar i dinamitzar grups de treball
CBT	- Proporcionar les eines per a la creació de taules rodones - Proporcionar informació als grups de treball
IDAEA-CSIC	Aportar coneixements sobre PMT
AMB	
Qui més es necessita? Amb qui puc col·laborar?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sector agrícola, sector industrial, administració, usuaris d'aigua regenerada, operadors, ACA, entitat local - Mitjans de comunicació, ONG o grups ja sensibilitzats - Per crear diferents grups de treball es necessitaran diferents tipus de perfil: tècnic, jurídic, sanitari, de comunicació, tècnics de producció de les indústries afectades, polítics, usuaris finals, etc. 	
Aquesta solució ja és compatible d'alguna manera? Si és així, com o per quin mecanisme?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Projectes de recerca - Sequera - Històries d'èxit - Estudis i experiències existents - R+D+I 	
2.- Prioritzar en el pressupost el finançament de tota la gestió del cicle de l'aigua (Governança)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	Prioritzar les inversions en funció de criteris de risc per a la salut i canvi climàtic
Sorigué	
IRTA	pot participar en projectes que proporcionen la visió de l'usuari final de l'aigua en l'agricultura
ASPCAT	
OdR	
Barcelona Regional	Administracions de suport
EURECAT	
CBT	Sol·licitar subvencions
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	Plans Directors
Qui més es necessita? Amb qui puc col·laborar?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gencat, ACA, Fons Europees són les que donen finançament - ACA - Empreses privades 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Administracions competents - Grups de recerca 	
Aquesta solució ja és compatible d'alguna manera? Si és així, com o per quin mecanisme?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sequera - Disminució de recursos - Multes per incompliment (indústria + operadors) - Augment de la taxa (optimització de l'ús dels recursos) 	
3.- Recerca sobre toxicitat, presència, riscos, etc. (Avaluació de la seguretat)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	Estudiar la presència de PMT en recursos i tractaments, avaluació de riscos envers la població
Sorigué	facilitadors de la recerca com a operadors d'EDAR i participants en projectes d'R+D. Concretament, per a PROMESSES, som els operadors de Montornés
IRTA	
ASPCAT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Col·laboració amb centres de recerca - Participació amb grups d'investigació de la presència i avaluació de riscos dels PMT
OdR	
Barcelona Regional	
EURECAT	Recerca sobre toxicitat i AOP
CBT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Treballar conjuntament amb centres de recerca - Realitzar més estudis de presència de PMT a la conca del Besòs Tordera per prioritzar la futura llista
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	
Qui més es necessita? Amb qui puc col·laborar?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Els operadors, ACA i grups de recerca (ASPCAT) - Grups de recerca (AB) - Universitats - Sorigué necessita organismes de recerca (Eurecat, IRTA, IDAEA-CSIC...), de fet ja col·laborem en molts projectes 	
Aquesta solució ja és compatible d'alguna manera? Si és així, com o per quin mecanisme?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sequera - Projectes de recerca - Capacitat tècnica de les agències implicades (R+D, gestió) - Eines informàtiques (IA, bases de dades, etc.) 	
4.- Control dels abocaments a la font (vigilància de la font de contaminació industrial) (Tractament/Seguiment)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	Comunicar a l'Administració corresponent els abocaments detectats en el control dels nostres recursos
Sorigué	Pot facilitar el control dels abocaments a les depuradores que operem
IRTA	
ASPCAT	
OdR	
Barcelona Regional	Administracions de suport
EURECAT	Tecnologia de detecció de vessaments
CBT	Realitzar comprovacions aleatòries en origen segons el tipus d'indústria per fer una exploració general de l'origen del PMT i consultar amb experts sobre tractaments alternatius en origen.
IDAEA-CSIC	Realitzar anàlisis

	Identificació, prioritització i seguiment dels contaminants emergents en el cas d'estudi.
AMB	
Qui més es necessita? Amb qui puc col·laborar?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participació de les EDAR (p. ex. per a la recollida de mostres), col·laboradors per a experiments d'eliminació i captura d'aquests contaminants en cultius - Autoritat local - ACA - Operador - Empreses privades - Ministeri - Indústria - Grups de recerca (R+D, universitats) 	
Aquesta solució ja és compatible d'alguna manera? Si és així, com o per quin mecanisme?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sequera - Més controls - Abocaments puntuals d'origen industrial (per exemple, 1,4-dioxà) 	
5.- Més R+D per a la recuperació de subproductes, recerca sobre processos redox (Tractament)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	Estudiar nous tractaments de potabilització/depuració, i optimitzar els existents per tal de minimitzar la formació de subproductes
Sorigué	
IRTA	
ASPCAT	Col·laboració amb centres de recerca
OdR	
Barcelona Regional	
EURECAT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - R+D en l'àmbit del tractament, gestió de subproductes - Tenir estudis i experiències pilot de tractaments i tecnologies - Recerca sobre toxicitat i AOP
CBT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Treballar conjuntament amb centres de recerca - Participar en la validació de plantes pilot / noves tecnologies a les nostres instal·lacions
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	
Qui més es necessita? Amb qui puc col·laborar?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Operadors i administracions en l'àmbit de l'aigua per atendre les diferents necessitats que puguin tenir - Universitats - Empreses - Centre d'R+D 	
Aquesta solució ja és compatible d'alguna manera? Si és així, com o per quin mecanisme?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sequera - Històries d'èxit - Estudis i experiències existents - R+D+I 	
6.- Incloure les substàncies PMT de manera explícita a la legislació (Governança)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	** Anticipar el control dels PMT no inclosos a la legislació
Sorigué	
IRTA	
ASPCAT	fer més avaluació del risc per a la salut dels PMT. Consulta amb altres CCAA i països amb més experiència
	Contactes amb el ministeri competent

OdR	
Barcelona Regional	
EURECAT	Metodologia d'identificació de substàncies i anàlisi de riscos
CBT	Facilitar casos pràctics com el cas de Montornès
IDAEA-CSIC	**Feu recomanacions sobre les substàncies a incloure Agrupació dels estudis d'investigació PMT dels diferents ens locals dins d'una mateixa conca o entre conques per compartir una llista de PMT detectats i prioritzar substàncies o mapejar punts calents.
AMB	regulació de l'abocament
Qui més es necessita? Amb qui puc col·laborar?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ACA - Col·laboració amb els diferents ens locals – operadors - Ministeri 	
Aquesta solució ja és compatible d'alguna manera? Si és així, com o per quin mecanisme?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sequera - Estudis i experiències existents - R+D+I - Abocaments puntuals d'origen industrial (per exemple, 1,4-dioxà) 	
7.- Comunicació dirigida i adaptada a cada tipus d'usuari (Social)	
Aj. Granollers	Podem col·laborar en la comunicació
Aigües de Barcelona	Treball de la part comunicativa orientada als diferents usos de l'aigua regenerada, especialment des de la vessant d'acceptació
Sorigué	
IRTA	
ASPCAT	Comunicació de riscos per a la salut
OdR	Organitzar jornades de trasllat i formació
Barcelona Regional	
EURECAT	Comunicació científica
CBT	Donar informació al sector industrial i agrícola
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	
Qui més es necessita? Amb qui puc col·laborar?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Òrgans de referència que poden donar un missatge tranquil·litzador - ACA - General 	
Aquesta solució ja és compatible d'alguna manera? Si és així, com o per quin mecanisme?	
<i>Sense resposta</i>	
8.- Protocol d'estimació de riscos per a la salut humana / metodologia d'avaluació de riscos (Avaluació de la seguretat / Governança)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	
Sorigué	
IRTA	Pot participar en l'efecte de l'ús d'aquesta aigua sobre el sòl i els cultius
ASPCAT	
OdR	
Barcelona Regional	
EURECAT	
CBT	
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	

Qui més es necessita? Amb qui puc col·laborar?	
<i>Sense resposta</i>	
Aquesta solució ja és compatible d'alguna manera? Si és així, com o per quin mecanisme?	
<i>Sense resposta</i>	
9.- Professionals de la comunicació en cadascun dels operadors i administracions de gestió de l'aigua (Social)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	
Sorigué	
IRTA	
ASPCAT	Comunicació de riscos per a la salut
OdR	Organitzar jornades de trasllat i formació
Barcelona Regional	
EURECAT	Comunicació científica
CBT	Donar informació al sector industrial i agrícola
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	
Qui més es necessita? Amb qui puc col·laborar?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ACA - General 	
Aquesta solució ja és compatible d'alguna manera? Si és així, com o per quin mecanisme?	
<i>Sense resposta</i>	
10.- Procés d'actualització àgil de la llista PMT (Governança)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	
Sorigué	
IRTA	
ASPCAT	Feu més avaluació del risc per a la salut dels PMT. Consulta amb altres CCAA i països amb més experiència
OdR	
Barcelona Regional	
EURECAT	Metodologia d'identificació de substàncies i anàlisi de riscos Suport mitjançant avaluacions de riscos per als ecosistemes i la salut humana per a l'elaboració de la llista
CBT	Facilitar casos pràctics com el cas de Montornès
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	Regulació de l'abocament
Qui més es necessita? Amb qui puc col·laborar?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ACA 	
Aquesta solució ja és compatible d'alguna manera? Si és així, com o per quin mecanisme?	
<i>Sense resposta</i>	
11.- Preu variable en funció del consum i/o incentius a l'estalvi (Governança)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	
Sorigué	
IRTA	
ASPCAT	
OdR	
Barcelona Regional	Administracions de suport

EURECAT	Tecnologia de detecció de vessaments
CBT	
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	
Qui més es necessita? Amb qui puc col·laborar?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Autoritat local - ACA - Operador - Empreses privades 	
Aquesta solució ja és compatible d'alguna manera? Si és així, com o per quin mecanisme?	
<i>Sense resposta</i>	
12.- Finançament tractaments EDARs mitjançant co-responsabilitat (Nova Directiva Aigües Residuals)	
Aj. Granollers	
Aigües de Barcelona	
Sorigué	
IRTA	
ASPCAT	
OdR	
Barcelona Regional	Administracions de suport
EURECAT	
CBT	Aplicar subvencions
IDAEA-CSIC	
AMB	Plans directors
Qui més es necessita? Amb qui puc col·laborar?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ACA - Empreses privades 	
Aquesta solució ja és compatible d'alguna manera? Si és així, com o per quin mecanisme?	
<i>Sense resposta</i>	

6. Conclusió

L'estructura dels tallers va donar lloc a una llista d'accions sobre com tractar les substàncies PM(T) durant la reutilització de l'aigua a la Conca del riu Besòs. Anant una mica més enllà, els agents van identificar les accions que constitueixen el primer pas cap a la reutilització segura i rendible de les aigües residuals per al reg. El primer pas identificat pels grups d'interès és la creació de grups de treball/taules rodones on tots els sectors de la societat puguin participar i oferir els seus coneixements/inquietuds per crear una estratègia comunal. El mateix taller de parts interessades i els seus participants es poden veure com un punt de partida per a aquest grup de treball.

Tots els interessats van coincidir que la reutilització d'aigües residuals per a l'agricultura hauria de ser una part integral de l'estratègia de gestió de l'aigua a la conca del riu Besòs, fins i tot donant una gran importància a la reutilització potable a considerar. No obstant això, les preguntes de qui paga i quant segueixen obertes. En conseqüència, les accions relacionades amb el finançament del tractament de PM(T) es veuen menys factibles.

Per a moltes de les solucions, actualment no hi ha suport institucional per a la seva implementació, cosa que posa de manifest la necessitat que els responsables polítics participin en grups de treball a nivell local. Més enllà dels responsables polítics, les solucions i el suport a la implementació que

ofereixen els participants posen de manifest la necessitat de col·laboració i comunicació intersectorials a la conca del riu Besòs per abordar amb èxit l'escassetat d'aigua. Aquest procés de taller de co-creació serveix com a exercici d'aquest enfocament "a tot el sistema" sobre el qual els actors locals poden construir avançant.

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Topic: LC-GD-8-1-2020 - Innovative, systemic zero-pollution solutions to protect health, environment, and natural resources from persistent and mobile chemicals

Preventing Recalcitrant Organic Mobile Industrial chemicals for Circular Economy in the soil-sediment-water System

D5.6 Annex E

Summary of Co-creation Stakeholder Workshops for the Marche & Lazio Regions (CS4)

Developing a system-wide, zero pollution strategy to support management of landfill leachate

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1. Background

1.1 Current Situation

In Italy, there are multiple locations that must deal with landfill leachate. Currently, it is not standard practice to use treatment technologies to remove substances that are persistent (P), mobile (M) and toxic (T), otherwise known as PM(T)s. However, these technologies are likely to be required or wanted in the future to pre-treat landfill leachate before it is combined with municipal wastewater. Efficient leachate pre-treatment can produce municipal sludge and effluent that are less contaminated with PMTs and is therefore important from environmental and public health perspectives – certainly when there are circular economic ambitions, such as water reuse or material recovery (e.g. for fertilization). Additionally, pre-treatment may be needed to comply with EU directives, such as the updated Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (7108/24), which requires monitoring for, among others, per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and several other organic compounds, including pharmaceuticals.

1.2 PROMISCES Case Study

At the Jesi wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) in Ancona, Italy, municipal wastewater from the Marche region and leachate from contaminated sites is treated. This is the site of a case study that is part of the EU-funded research project PROMISCES. At this site, the PROMISCES partner Università Politecnica delle Marche (UNIVPM) is testing a more efficient pre-treatment of landfill leachate using reverse osmosis and nanofiltration to remove PM(T)s/PFAS. Aside from pre-treating landfill leachate, this technology could also be relevant for other highly contaminated water sources, such as effluents from industry. In addition, the case study is examining the use of pyrolysis as an alternative to incineration to treat the resulting sludge and concentrate.

Implementation of such an additional pre-treatment step for landfill leachate is not straightforward. Aside from the technological aspects, there are also other relevant factors, for example, financial, technical know-how, governance, monitoring requirements, and environmental and human risk assessments. Therefore, an implementation strategy is needed that considers the system view on both the barriers to implementation and potential solutions to overcome such barriers.

2. Co-Creation Process to Create Zero-Pollution Strategies

To create a viable strategy for dealing with landfill leachate that considers the presence of micro-contaminants, a system view is needed on both the problem(s) and potential solutions. For this purpose, PROMISCES organized a co-creation process with stakeholders. This interactive co-creation workshop took place on April 19, 2024 at ACEA SpA, centro congressi "La Fornace" with a diverse group of 20 external stakeholders. The goals of this in-person workshop were to (Figure 1):

- Identify barriers and other factors that need to be addressed to further management of landfill leachate in the Marche and Lazio regions
- Define solutions to overcome these barriers
- Co-create an interdisciplinary, system-wide strategy that incorporates the defined solutions and needed actors

To prepare the stakeholders for the ensuing discussion on barriers and solutions, PROMISCES created a preliminary online survey where participants could provide barriers to landfill leachate management and categorize the barriers as financial, technical, social, legislative, environmental, public health. More on this in the following section.

Figure 1. Structure and agenda of the in-person stakeholder workshop.

3. Co-Creation Workshop

3.1 Introduction

The workshop began with an explanation of the co-creation process. Additionally, the context and problem surrounding landfill leachate were explained together with an explanation of the case study activities.

3.2 Workshop Part 1: Barriers & Enablers

3.2.1 Identifying Barriers

We used the results of the initial survey to establish a list of barriers. During the first part of the co-creation workshop, the participants reflected on the barriers identified in the survey and added to the list as needed. The output from this session is presented in Table 1, with barriers listed per category. The barriers indicated in bold were prioritised in the next workshop phase (see below).

Table 1. Barriers and enablers for the management of landfill leachate. The bolded text are the prioritized barriers.

BARRIERS
Environmental health
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No political agreement regarding responsibilities • Lack of environmental compliance limits for certain contaminants • Carbon footprint that can be generated • Emissions from incineration of concentrated waste, which is currently the standard practice • Rapid analysis and management of concentrate combustion is needed • Lack of a national monitoring program for PFAS (in the environment) • PMTs affect multiple matrices, need broad study
Public health
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of regulations • Lack of a national monitoring program (for health) • Lack of risk analysis methodologies • Need impact assessments in the area surrounding the treatment & incineration plants
Social
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Not in my backyard” syndrome regarding landfill location and incineration • No awareness or knowledge of the level of PFAS in various products • Lack of proper communication to the public regarding PFAS • Insufficient knowledge dissemination targeting plant operators about the state-of-the-art on treatment systems
Technical
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interference with other substances of the leachate • Frequency of membrane/active carbon replacement • Dealing with concentrate from reverse osmosis (RO) • Low removal efficiency of PFAS from all the processes available at reasonable cost • Need to modify treatment train of existing plants • Cost of technical solutions (need CAPEX/OPEX) • Analytical difficulty for monitoring • Lack of monitoring programs for PFAS • Overall deficit of plants able to treat PFAS (too few and existing plants are saturated) • Combined treatment of landfill leachate together with urban waste water dilutes the leachate, leading to low removal efficiency • Restrictions on other parameters (e.g. ammonia) for choosing of the technical solution

BARRIERS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leachates with different incoming PFAS loads could apply different solutions • Lack of monitoring plans to guide the appropriate technological choice
Financial
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy cost • Installation and maintenance cost • High costs of managing/treating waste that contains PFAS • Long investment payback period for implementing new technologies
Legislative, Governance
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slow bureaucracy for releasing landfill permits, answering clarification requests, etc. • Lack of technical competence and expertise by competent authority regarding PFAS • Lack of competence between the regions (see point above) • Obsolete law frame, different regulations/laws • Restrictive interpretation of the law • Lack of a clear and unambiguous regulation on limit values for PFAS discharges, products • No specific compliance limits established by European/national laws • Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) covers pharmaceuticals and does not address PFAS • Integration/Standardisation between standard (waste) water and drinking water legislation needed • Lack of EU legislation regulating the production of PFAS-free products and packaging • Undefined risk analysis procedures to set regulatory limits

3.2.2 Prioritizing Barriers

After finalizing the lists of barriers, the participants voted on the priority of the barriers using red, yellow and green stickers (see Figure 2. 32). The most important barriers (those with the highest number of red stickers) are indicated in bold in Table 1 above and are listed below.

Figure 2. 3The workshop participants used red, yellow and green stickers to identify the barriers that should be prioritized. Red means highest priority.

Most prioritized barriers had a link to the categories of public/environmental health (3), governance (2), societal (2) and technical (2). Additionally, one priority barrier was identified within the financial category. Note that the barriers can be related to multiple categories (Table 2).

Table 2. The complete list of prioritized barriers.

Prioritized barrier	Category
1. Lack of regulations, compliance limits / limit values	Governance/public health
2. Slow bureaucratic system for releasing landfill permits, answering clarification requests, etc.	Governance
3. Lack of risk analysis methodologies	Public health
4. Lack of suitable monitoring programs for PFAS	Public health/environmental health/technical
5. Installation and maintenance costs	Financial
6. Lack of proper communication to the public regarding PFAS and to plant operators about the state-of-the-art on treatment systems	Social
7. Lack of societal awareness of the level of PFAS in various products	Social
8. Lack of suitable technological solutions (closure of the cycle and analytical difficulties for control)	Technical

3.3 Workshop Part 2: Identifying Solutions

3.3.1 Brainstorming Solutions

The next step was to identify solutions for the eight prioritized barriers. This started with a ‘brain-dump’ by the participants, in which they provided as many solutions as possible for each of the identified barriers (see Figure 4. 53).

Figure 4. 5The participants used sticky notes to brainstorm solutions for the eight prioritized barriers.

The results of this brainstorm of solutions are indicated in Table 3.

Table 3. Solutions proposed by the participants for the eight prioritized barriers.

Governance	
1.	<p>Barrier: Lack of regulations, compliance limits / limit values</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ban on PFAS • Establish common limit values at the EU level for clean water to be discharged into surface waters • Quickly enact rules banning the use of PFAS in industry (primarily that may affect the food chain) • Rapidly enact rules setting limit values for urban and industrial wastewater discharges
2.	<p>Barrier: Slow bureaucratic system for releasing landfill permits, answering clarification requests, etc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a guidance for public authorities on implementing new rules and regulations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Technical ○ Administrative (procedures) • Provide guidelines for administrative urgency procedures for landfill permit authorisation
Public/environmental health	
3.	<p>Barrier: Lack of risk analysis methodologies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draft a guidance at EU/IT level • Zero-risk should be the objective

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To promote a consensus of what has been developed or already available at national level, such as latest methods developed or currently under study <p>4. Barrier: Lack of suitable monitoring programs for PFAS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insert in legislation a minimum frequency of monitoring and analytes to be searched Share methodologies for statistical & technical data analysis Common PFAS database (sharing) (see EU Phoenix Project) on leachate Public (EU/IT) financing of leachate monitoring to support local environmental agencies Establish bodies and laboratories implementing the monitoring plan Feasibility studies on monitoring programs Develop monitoring programs on environmental matrices, surface water, groundwater, soil, homogeneous production discharges for each region
Financial
<p>5. Barrier: Installation and maintenance costs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The costs should be borne not by the citizens but specific funds should be provided by the states Implement a tax on companies that use PFAS as part of their production to disincentivize its use Application of the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) criterion at the European level
Social
<p>6. Barrier: Lack of proper communication to the public regarding PFAS and to plant operators about the state-of-the-art on treatment systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public consultation on PFAS in primary raw materials and common products Advertising campaign to discourage the use of PFAS-containing products Public opinion information on PFAS-containing products Covered by EPR (Extended Producer Responsibility) Implementation of new regulations for the use of water for human consumption <p>7. Barrier: Lack of societal awareness of the level of PFAS in various products</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inform consumers on which products contain PFAS to influence consumption Product labelling; indication of the presence of PFAS in consumer goods Organization of events for experts or the population
Technical
<p>8. Barrier: Lack of suitable technological solutions (closure of the cycle and analytical difficulties for control)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote state-of-the-art knowledge of technologies to plant operators Encourage research and innovation to industrialise pilot projects Technical guidance on different technologies to remove PFAS from leachate Standardize analyses that rely on fluorine content for quantifying PFAS

3.3.2 Selecting Priority Actions

After the ‘brain-dump’ round, the identified solutions were grouped, discussed and prioritized in a plenary setting. Based on this discussion, the following priority actions were identified:

1. Limit the use of PFAS in industry and encourage research for the production of new, less impactful molecules. Economic leverage (taxation for impactful products and concessions for sustainable ones). Product certification and labeling system.
2. Quickly define the limits for PFAS in discharge into surface waters and sewers

3. Define clear monitoring program and methodology (analytical methods, identification of indicator parameters for specific matrix) for managing leachate.
4. Develop guidelines and training courses for public administration to reduce the bureaucratic delays of landfill permit authorizations and interpreting new rules/regulations. Suggestion to create these guidelines in tabular form to ease understanding.
5. Define guidelines for risk analyses for emerging contaminants at the European level. Knowledge and best practices from researchers should be collected and shared to support this.
6. Provide public funding for monitoring programs and finding solutions.
7. Expand the extended producer responsibility (EPR) system to cover PFAS to reduce costs and cover not only the costs of treatment, but also those of monitoring and research.
8. Implement labeling system for products containing PFAS and promote actions on green public procurement.
9. Public opinion information programs (at different age levels including school age).
10. Promote awareness among plant managers about existing technical solutions.
11. Raise awareness in the National System for Environmental Protection (SNPA) for the need to issue guidelines and best practices.

3.4 Workshop Part 3: Towards a strategy

In the third part of the workshop, there were two activities:

1. Stakeholders identified actions for themselves for each of the solutions;
2. Stakeholders judged the feasibility of their identified actions using the colour of the sticky notes (green = more feasible; yellow = less feasible).

The result of this activity is presented in the table below. The stakeholders were not able to identify actions for every solution during the workshop. The solutions where no action was identified are not included in Table 4 (Solutions 1, 6, 7). In some instances, a stakeholder listed themselves as being involved in implementing the solution but did not specify an action. These entries are included in the table as “no action included”.

Table 44. The results from the third part of the workshop. For each solution, the organisation indicated actions for themselves, and judged the feasibility using the colour of the sticky note. Green means highly feasible, yellow means moderately feasible. In the public version, the organisation names are replaced by the respective sector.

Priority Solution	Supporting Actions and Respective Organisation
Solution 2: Quickly define the limits for PFAS in discharge into surface waters and sewers	Org. name not provided Activate wastewater monitoring campaigns coordinated by a public body
	Research Scientific technical support on the environmental part if necessary
	Public administration Support national environmental ministry to set up limits
	Public administration Support for the definition of limits
Solution 2: Quickly define the limits for PFAS in discharge into surface waters and sewers	Org. name not provided Activate wastewater monitoring campaigns coordinated by a public body
	Research Scientific technical support on the environmental part if necessary
	Public administration

Priority Solution	Supporting Actions and Respective Organisation
	Support national environmental ministry to set up limits Public administration Support for the definition of limits
Solution 3: Define clear monitoring program and methodology (analytical methods, identification of indicator parameters for specific matrix) for managing leachate	Org. name not provided Develop cost-effective methodologies in laboratories for PFAS analysis and indicators with the support of other national and international laboratories Water operator Can organize periodic sampling programs for the detection of substances in the effluents of its treatment plants Public health No action included Public administration Implement monitoring plans (definition and execution) Public administration Share experience on PFAS analysis Research Support for the definition of an environmental monitoring program
Solution 4: Develop guidelines and training courses for public administration to reduce the bureaucratic delays of landfill permit authorizations and interpreting new rules/regulations. Suggestion to create these guidelines in tabular form to ease understanding.	Public health No action listed Research The guidelines must be agreed upon with SNPA and entities issuing the authorization Public administration Support to draft guidance on technical & administrative aspects based on Veneto's experience Public administration Participation in training courses for public administration
Solution 5: Define guidelines for risk analyses for emerging contaminants at the European level. Knowledge and best practices from researchers should be collected and shared to support this.	Public administration Support for defining guidelines through data elaboration Environmental association Collect best practices and case studies Public health Define guidelines for risk assessment at the European level Research Technical and scientific support for the definition of environmental guidelines Research / Public health On the basis of polluted soils and landfill reuse analysis guidance
Solution 8: Implement labeling system for products containing PFAS and promote actions on green public procurement.	Environmental association Monitoring and dissemination through the Green Procurement Observatory.
Solution 9: Public opinion information programs (at different age levels including school age).	Environmental association Before the formation of the teaching staff (missing) Water operator Can organize: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events for schools (various levels)

Priority Solution	Supporting Actions and Respective Organisation
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal training • Awareness events for citizens
	No org listed Lack of study of alternatives to propose to consumers (when informed)
	Public health No action listed
	Research Environmental part
	Public administration Environmental education for citizens and in schools
	Public administration Specific environmental education programme with school [SE]
Solution 10: Promote awareness among plant managers about technical existing solutions.	Public administration Meetings/confrontations with managers on the technologies developed at the current state Public administration Contribute to share Veneto experience with support of local landfill management companies Technology provider Can support communication of the experience made by Italian clusters and the entire PROMISCES project. Thematic outsourcing to define also adequately in vision of future limits taking configurations as much as possible optimized also with reference to PFAS. Support needed at legislative level (need to have reference limits).
Solution 11: Raise awareness in the National System for Environmental Protection (SNPA) for the need to issue guidelines and best practices.	Public administration Organize meeting between environmental agencies for shared request to SNPA for guidance and best practices Public administration Attend SNPA's working group on PFAS-containing leachate management Research No action listed Environmental association Political lobbying

5. Reflections and Conclusion

The structure of the workshop resulted in an action list of how to deal with PM(T) substances in landfill leachate. The workshop made clear that an action plan is needed, and priority actions for this were identified that focus on governance and legislation, social and financial aspects. This highlights the importance of boundary conditions that must be met to address problems along the circular economy route, thereby enabling the prevention or substitution of PM(T) substances or the implementation of technical solutions.

Due to the time constraint of the stakeholder workshop, the various actions from the involved stakeholders are merely listed in the following table, without specifics regarding timing or priority. It is therefore recommended that the PROMISCES case study 4 leads follow up with the stakeholders in order to transition these suggested actions into a comprehensive and collaborative strategy.